

4th Decision Science Alliance International
Summer Conference, DSA ISC 2026

HUMAN-AI
COLLABORATION FOR
REAL-WORLD
DECISION-MAKING

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

June 18-19, 2026 | MADRID
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

GENERAL CHAIRS

Álvaro García
Sánchez

Ángel A. Juan

Raffaele Maccioni

PROGRAM COMMITTEE CHAIRS

Álvaro García
Sánchez

Ángel A. Juan

Miguel Gutiérrez

Miguel Ortega
Mier

Joaquín Ordieres
Meré

ISBN

978-84-09-87576-4

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.20720602

This **Book of Abstracts** has been *edited by*:
Carlos García-Gerbolés and Marc Escoto Gomar

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INCLUSIVE AUTOMATION AND SIZE RECOMMENDATION ALGORITHMS IN THE FASHION INDUSTRY: A DIGITAL HUMANITIES AND DECISION SCIENCE APPROACH .7	
MODELS AND METHODS FOR POLLUTION-BASED ZONING: THE CASE OF LOMBARDY	10
GEOSPATIAL DATA ENRICHMENT BY ADVANCED ANALYTICS	11
A LARGE NEIGHBORHOOD SEARCH HEURISTIC FOR THE DIAL-A-RIDE PROBLEM IN MODULAR TRANSIT SYSTEMS.....	13
PRODUCTION RESCHEDULING BASED ON MULTI-AGENT AUCTIONS.....	15
SCHEDULING RECOMMENDER SYSTEM FOR STEEL PRODUCTION	17
HOW AI TOOLKIT SOLUTIONS ARE DISRUPTING GO-TO-MARKET STRATEGIES AND STREAMLINING BRAND DEVELOPMENT	19
EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF OSCILLATOR NETWORKS WITH A COMPREHENSIVE SUITE OF SYNCHRONIZATION METRICS.....	20
MODELING AND LINEARIZATION ANALYSIS OF A TOTAL ENERGY MINLP FOR SINGLE-TRUCK, MULTIPLE-DRONE LAST MILE DELIVERY	21
FROM PORTFOLIO OPTIMIZATION TO STRUCTURAL DECISION-MAKING: A STRUCTURAL HEURISTIC THEORY OF CLIDUCTS, EVIDENCE FROM LARGE COMPANIES	22
PHYSIOLOGICAL MARKERS AND THEIR IMPACT ON DECISION-MAKING PERFORMANCE IN HIGH-STAKES COMMERCIAL AVIATION	23
OPERATIONALIZING HUMAN-AI COLLABORATION FOR HIGH-VOLUME PROJECT RISK MANAGEMENT	25
MULTIMODAL DIGITAL DECISION SUPPORT IN MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS: INTEGRATING REMOTE GAIT MONITORING AND MOBILE COGNITIVE ASSESSMENT FOR ECOLOGICALLY VALID DISEASE TRACKING.....	26
A DECISION-SUPPORT-ORIENTED ECOSYSTEM BUSINESS MODEL FRAMEWORK FOR DIGITAL PRODUCT-SERVICE SYSTEMS	27
AHP-DRIVEN SUPPLIER SELECTION WITH AN APPLICATION TO THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY	28
FORECASTING RENEWABLE ENERGY PRODUCTION IN A MULTIREGIONAL FRAMEWORK	29
SOLVING A ROUTING PROBLEM WITHOUT A ROUTING ALGORITHM: A CASE STUDY IN FOOD DISTRIBUTION.....	30
GNN MIXTURE-OF-EXPERTS FOR SEGMENT-LEVEL TRAVEL TIME PREDICTION IN LAST-MILE DELIVERY	31
CLUSTERING UNIVERSITY DROPOUT PROFILES: A COMPARISON OF UNSUPERVISED METHODS FOLLOWING PCA AND UMAP PREPROCESSING ON STEM STUDENTS	32
EBUDDY: A WORKFLOW ORCHESTRATOR FOR INDUSTRIAL HUMAN-MACHINE COLLABORATION.....	33

GRAPH-BASED RETRIEVAL-AUGMENTED PLANNING FOR ROBOTS WITH PROVENANCE-AWARE KNOWLEDGE.....	34
HUMAN-LLM COLLABORATIVE DECISION-MAKING FOR MANUFACTURING DISRUPTION MANAGEMENT IN INDUSTRY 5.0.....	35
A LOCAL-SEARCH-ENHANCED ITERATED GREEDY ALGORITHM FOR THE RANK PRICING PROBLEM WITH TIES.....	37
FROM PLANNING TO AGENTS: HOW ROBUST ARE LLM-GENERATED HEURISTICS?	38
AI DECISION-SUPPORT FOR ETHICAL CONTEXTS: INSIGHTS FROM WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT AND IMPLICATIONS FOR BUSINESS.....	39
DESIGN AND OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING IN A DUAL-DEGRADATION ASSET HEALTH INDEX MODEL FOR POWER TRANSFORMERS.....	40
FROM DOCUMENTATION TO PROCESS-CENTRIC DECISION-MAKING: DEPLOYING THE PIPES AND PUDDLES FRAMEWORK ON THE GRAPHIC ARTS SHOP FLOOR OF A SUPPORTED EMPLOYMENT CENTER.....	41
THE IMPACT OF DATA PREPROCESSING ON STUDENT DROPOUT PREDICTION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY AT A SPANISH TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY.....	43
FRAMEWORK FOR DEFINING FUTURE RESEARCH LINES ON SUSTAINABILITY-DRIVEN AI IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR.....	44
HACKING MATHEMATICS: A STEAM CURRICULUM INTEGRATING MATHEMATICS, 3D FABRICATION AND IOT FOR SOCIETY 5.0	45
SOLVING ROUTING PROBLEMS WITH MULTIPLE DRONES WITH INTERCEPTIONS	46
USING HIGH-RESOLUTION MODELING TO REDUCE BASIS RISK IN TROPICAL CYCLONE PARAMETRIC RISK TRANSFER STRUCTURES: A CASE STUDY.....	47
EXPLORING THE RANKINE VORTEX DYNAMICS USING CELLULAR AUTOMATA IN 2D COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS	48
PERCEPTION OF AI AND DIGITALIZATION IN THE SPANISH PIG SECTOR.....	49
BLOCKCHAIN FRAUD DETECTION FOR EXPLAINABLE FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS.....	50
FAST, FAITHFUL, AND FAIR: REAL-TIME PROBABILISTIC XAI VIA KNOWLEDGE DISTILLATION.....	51
AI MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR AUTONOMOUS DECISION-MAKING IN THE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY.....	52
A MULTISTART HEURISTIC FOR 3D BIN PACKING AND ROUTING PROBLEM IN WAREHOUSE AUTOMATION.....	53
OPTIMIZATION OF ORDER BATCHING AND SCHEDULING WITH SOFT TIME-WINDOW DUE DATES.....	54
INTERACTIVE ONLINE TOURIST ITINERARY RECOMMENDER WITH DYNAMIC OPTIMISATION	55
INTERPRETABLE AI FOR HUMAN-CENTERED WAREHOUSE PICKING SEGMENTATION..	56
BEHAVIOURAL SIMULATION OF CONSUMER SEGMENTS USING DIGITAL TWINS.....	57

A MIXED INTEGER PROGRAMMING APPROACH FOR COST-OPTIMAL HETEROGENEOUS NETWORK PLANNING	59
A GENDER LENS ON TRANSPORT APPLICATIONS IN BUSINESS ANALYTICS AND OPERATIONS RESEARCH.....	60
A DECISION SUPPORT MODULE FOR ENVIRONMENTAL-DRIVEN SUPPLIER SELECTION IN MANUFACTURING PROCUREMENT	61
A MODE-AVAILABILITY CONSTRAINED VARIANT AND UNCERTAINTY-AWARE EVALUATION PROCEDURE FOR FLOATING CATCHMENT AREA METHODS.....	62
HUMAN-CENTRIC DECISION SUPPORT FOR SMART FACTORIES: A MULTIMODAL APPROACH TO HUMAN-MACHINE INTERACTION.....	63
LARGE LANGUAGE MODEL BASED ENTITY RELATION MAPPING FOR SUPPLY CHAIN VISIBILITY.....	64
GREENET: A SIMULATION-OPTIMIZATION DECISION-SUPPORT FRAMEWORK FOR WIRELESS ACCESS POINT LOCALIZATION	65
A CONTEXT-ENRICHED CAPACITATED VEHICLE ROUTING FRAMEWORK: INTEGRATING OPTIMIZATION, GEOSPATIAL INTELLIGENCE, AND ADMINISTRATIVE ANALYTICS	66
TOWARDS PLANNERS SEGMENTATION IN REAL-WORLD VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEMS	67
LEAFs: LINEAR EDGE-TO-CLOUD LATENCY-AWARE FORMULATION FOR SERVICE PLACEMENT	68
RECENT AI APPROACHES FOR ONCOLOGICAL DISEASE DIAGNOSIS: AN OVERVIEW AND EMERGING FUTURE DIRECTIONS	69
TAG EXTRACTION FROM MEDICAL HISTORY THROUGH LLMS	70
MACHINE LEARNING-DRIVEN BI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION OF HETEROLOGOUS AND HOMOLOGOUS COVID-19 VACCINE DISTRIBUTION NETWORK	71
AN ONTOLOGY FOR MANUFACTURING OPERATIONS AS A SERVICE.....	73
REDUCING BIOLOGICAL UNCERTAINTY IN PREVENTIVE ONCOLOGY: A BAYESIAN DECISION FRAMEWORK INTEGRATING DYNAMIC METABOLIC PROFILING (DMA-PPOP)	74
AI-BASED OPTIMIZATION FOR FACILITY LOCATION UNDER CHANGING CAPACITY CONDITIONS	75
BEYOND STATISTICAL CONVERGENCE: OPTIMIZED SEMANTIC MODELS FOR STRATEGIC MARKETING	76
ABSOLUT VODKA: FROM HUMAN INTELLIGENCE TO HUMAN-AI COLLABORATION IN REAL-WORLD MARKETING DECISION-MAKING.....	77
INCORPORATING AI IN ECOSYSTEMS GOVERNANCE: ARCHETYPES AND IMPLEMENTATION FRAMEWORK.....	78

ID 14

INCLUSIVE AUTOMATION AND SIZE RECOMMENDATION ALGORITHMS IN THE FASHION INDUSTRY: A DIGITAL HUMANITIES AND DECISION SCIENCE APPROACH

Alicia Bonillo Calero¹[0000-0001-6639-5912]

Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Escola d'Art i Superior de Disseny de València
(EASD València), ISEACV a.bonillocalero@iseacv.gva.es

Abstract. This research proposes an automated size recommendation prototype based on anthropometric measurements and absolute-error minimization strategies. Developed in Python from European anthropo-metric datasets and industrial dimensional correspondence systems, the model compares chest, waist, hip, and height measurements to generate approximate clothing size recommendations. The study approaches the algorithm not only as a computational tool but also as a mediating sys-tem between body representation, user experience, and decision-making processes within the framework of digital humanities.

Keywords: fashion sizing · anthropometry · digital humanities · deci-sion science · automated recommendation systems

1 Introduction

The lack of standardization in clothing sizing systems constitutes one of the main structural challenges within the contemporary fashion industry. Variability be-tween brands, the absence of unified anthropometric criteria, and differences between grading systems complicate the accurate selection of garments, partic-ularly in digital environments where users cannot physically try on products before purchasing them [1].

This situation generates uncertainty in the purchasing experience and re-inforces body perceptions conditioned by rigid and insufficiently inclusive clas-sification systems[4]. In parallel, the incorporation of computational tools into processes of body mediation and dimensional classification has begun to trans-form traditional anthropometric correspondence systems[5].

The present research proposes a computational prototype for automated size recommendation based on body measurements and absolute-error minimization strategies. The study is situated within the field of digital humanities by under-standing the algorithm not merely as a technical tool, but as a mediating system between body representation, user experience, and decision-making processes[6]

2 Methodology

The system was developed in Python using European anthropometric datasets [2] and industrial dimensional correspondence parameters[1]. The model requires four primary anthropometric variables: chest (P), waist (C), hip circumference (Ca), and height (E). Based on these data, the algorithm compares user measurements against a predefined equivalence database and calculates cumulative deviation through an absolute-error-based fit index. The recommendation process prioritizes the dimensional correspondence with the lowest cumulative anthropometric deviation.

$$Fit\ Index = |P_u - P_t| + |C_u - C_t| + |Ca_u - Ca_t| + |E_u - E_t|$$

Fig. 1. Formula used to calculate the anthropometric fit index.

The current model does not yet incorporate differentiated weighting between body variables, although this possibility is considered as a future research direction to improve precision according to garment typologies and fabric behavior.

The operational workflow allows users to select a body category, manually enter measurements, and automatically generate a dimensional recommendation together with its approximate European equivalence.

Fig. 2. Functional workflow of the automated recommendation system.

3 Preliminary Results

Initial experimental tests have demonstrated the functional viability of the proto-type across different body profiles. The system shows consistency in dimensional assignment based on manually entered measurements, highlighting the potential of the model as a decision-support tool for garment selection processes.

Although the research remains in an exploratory phase and does not yet include large-scale statistical validation or comparative analysis with commercial platforms, the proposal enables reflection on the relationship between automation, body representation, and digital inclusion within the contemporary fashion ecosystem[5][6].

From a digital humanities perspective, the algorithm operates as a body interpretation device that translates anthropometric data into automated decisions, revealing how computational systems actively participate in shaping contemporary experiences of dressing and body classification.

References

1. Ashdown, S.: *Sizing in Clothing: Developing Effective Sizing Systems for Ready-to-Wear Clothing*. Woodhead Publishing, Cambridge (2007)
2. Sizing SUDOE.: *Estudio antropométrico de la población del sudoeste europeo*. Instituto de Biomecánica de Valencia, Valencia (2015)
3. Song, H.K., Ashdown, S.P.: An exploratory study of the validity of visual fit assessment from three-dimensional scans. *Clothing and Textiles Research Journal* 28(4), 263–278 (2010)
4. McKinney, E., Shin, E.: Body cathexis and fit satisfaction in apparel consumption. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management* 18(3), 315–329 (2014)
5. Manovich, L.: *The Language of New Media*. MIT Press, Cambridge (2001)
6. Drucker, J.: *Digital Humanities and Interpretation*. University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis (2020)

MODELS AND METHODS FOR POLLUTION-BASED ZONING: THE CASE OF LOMBARDY

Alberto Ceselli¹[000-0002-0983-2706] and Marco Premoli¹[0000-0002-3297-2133]

Università degli Studi di Milano, Department of Computer Science, 18, via Celoria,
20133, Milano (Italy) alberto.ceselli@unimi.it ✉ marco.premoli@unimi.it

European legislation [1] requires Member States to establish territorial zoning schemes to ensure representative air quality monitoring and enable differentiated environmental policy measures. In this context, we investigate how the current administrative subdivision adopted by the Lombardy Region (Italy) could be complemented by quantitative approaches that better capture the dynamics of atmospheric pollution.

The zoning framework proposed by the *Regional Agency for Environmental Protection* of Lombardy (ARPA) is primarily based on population density and morphological characteristics. As an alternative, we define a distance metric relying exclusively on municipal-level air pollution data and apply agglomerative clustering algorithms with spatial contiguity constraints [2, 3], together with a mathematical programming model.

Using the open Air Emissions Inventory dataset [4], we identify distinctive emission clusters, including the isolated Milan metropolitan area and low-impact mountainous zones, and compare the resulting zoning configurations with the ARPA proposal through key performance indicators measuring intra-cluster similarity and inter-cluster separation.

The proposed model demonstrates that integrating emission data with geographic contiguity produces coherent and interpretable territorial partitions, effectively revealing significant emission patterns.

Keywords: zoning · contiguity-constrained clustering · mathematical programming · air quality.

References

1. European Parliament and Council. Directive 2008/50/ec of the european parliament and of the council of 21 may 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for europe. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 152:1-44, 2008. ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2008/50/oj>.
2. Guillaume Guénard and Pierre Legendre. Hierarchical Clustering with Contiguity Constraint in *R*. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 103(7):1-26, 2022.
3. Leandro Miranda, José Viterbo, and Flávia Bernardini. A framework for spatial regionalization composed of novel clustering-based algorithms under spatial contiguity constraints. *Transactions in GIS*, 26(4):1775-1800, 2022.
4. ARPA Lombardia. Inventario delle emissioni. <https://www.arpalombardia.it/temi-ambientali/aria/inventario/inventario-delle-emissioni/>, 2023.

ID 43

GEOSPATIAL DATA ENRICHMENT BY ADVANCED ANALYTICS

Marco Casazza¹[0000-0002-3701-4241], Alberto Ceselli¹[0000-0002-0983-2706], and
Marco Premoli¹[0000-0002-3297-2133]

OptLab, Dipartimento di Informatica, Università degli Studi di Milano, Via Celoria
18 Milano (IT) name.surname@unimi.it

Abstract. In responding to climate changes, and general system disruptions, institutional decision-makers are asked to make critical decisions. Their policies have a significant impact on people and the environment. One of the objectives of the GRINS foundation, funded by the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan, is to build a digital platform, whose name is AMELIA [1], to foster a proactive prevention perspective.

We share insights on ADALINA, a project carried out by OptLab on GRINS open calls. OptLab contributed with a research and innovation action, equipping AMELIA with decision support tools for ex-ante evaluation and planning.

Our project is built on two pillars: data enrichment through georeferencing and through advanced analytics. It involves the creation of advanced analytics modules that use computational methods, based on simulation models and optimization algorithms, as well as a geo-enrichment service capable of integrating geospatial data both with contextual data from multiple sources and with data dynamically generated by the analytics modules. The project has enabled innovation in the methodological, algorithmic and computational aspects, as well as development of industrial software. It led to the full integration of our advanced modules for data processing and decision support within AMELIA. The outcome is in fact a suite of services for geospatial data enrichment, which is currently deployed and accessible through the AMELIA platform.

Thanks to our tools, an AMELIA user can combine geospatial data sources, even when they are defined on different geometries over the same territory. For example, they can combine maps of municipal boundaries, defined as compositions of polygons, and weather conditions given over regular grids, estimating actual disruption risk values for city districts. They can further enrich the data with ex-ante prescriptive analytics assessments. For example, they can combine risk maps with the locations of hospitals in the same region, obtaining a new map, which is an optimal partitioning the territory into zones of homogeneous level of service. They can also combine maps with road networks to assess the impact of pollution on people, and indications of adjustments to reduce it.

Keywords: Decision Support Tools · Climate Changes · Research and Innovation actions.

References

1. GRINS Foundation “AMELIA: a data platform to understand and govern complexity” (last access March 2026) <https://grins.it/progetto/piattaforma-amelia>

A LARGE NEIGHBORHOOD SEARCH HEURISTIC FOR THE DIAL-A-RIDE PROBLEM IN MODULAR TRANSIT SYSTEMS

Riccardo Giusti^{*1}, Vida Gallo², Gabriele Pirilli², Abdelouahab Moubane¹,
Tiziana Delmastro¹, and Edoardo Fadda²

¹ Future Cities & Communities Research Domain, LINKS Foundation, Turin, Italy

² Department of Mathematical Sciences, Politecnico di Torino, Turin, Italy
*riccardo.giusti@linksfoundation.com

Keywords: Modular Transit Systems, Dial-a-Ride Problem, Large Neighborhood Search.

Modular transit systems have recently emerged as a promising approach for improving the flexibility and efficiency of on-demand mobility services. By allowing individual units to dynamically couple and decouple, modular vehicles enable fleets to adapt their capacity to passenger demand, forming platoons whose size can change over time [1]. In addition, modular configurations may enable in-motion transfer operations [2], where passenger-carrying modules can be exchanged between vehicles without requiring passengers to disembark, thereby reducing transfer and waiting times. Operating modules in coordinated platoons may also provide operational benefits, including improved vehicle capacity utilization and potential cost savings, as platoons can achieve higher energy efficiency, addressing challenges such as overcrowded vehicles during peak hours and underutilized capacity during off-peak periods or in areas with low passenger demand density [3].

Modular vehicles are typically divided into powered modules, which are equipped with propulsion and control systems and may be either fully autonomous or operated by human drivers, and trailer modules, which are used solely to provide additional passenger capacity when coupled to a powered module. The long-term vision of modular transit systems is often discussed within a fully autonomous mobility paradigm, as this configuration could provide the greatest operational benefits and service coverage. However, their practical implementation must account for real-world operational constraints and the current technological and regulatory limitations of fully autonomous systems.

Despite the advantages offered by modular vehicles, planning such systems presents not only legal and technological challenges but also makes decision-making more difficult in these dynamic systems. Compared to classical routing and scheduling problems, accounting for the features of modular transit systems significantly increases the complexity of solving those problems. Existing studies typically focus on fixed or partially structured service configurations or on fully flexible routing schemes, which address individual aspects such as capacity adaptation, routing, and passenger transfers independently rather than in an integrated manner. This simplification is motivated by

the computational complexity that arises when these decision layers are considered jointly, as integrating modular capacity reconfiguration, platooning, and module coupling and decoupling leads to large-scale optimization problems that are difficult to solve on realistic networks.

This work aims to address gaps in the literature by proposing a routing optimization model for modular transit systems, by integrating key decisions including vehicle routing, passenger assignment, and module reconfiguration. The problem is formulated as a Mixed-Integer Linear Programming model extending the classical Dial-a-Ride Problem (DARP), and aims to minimize operational costs while limiting unserved demand. Constraints capturing essential features of modular transit systems, including dynamic coupling and decoupling, platoon formation, and passenger transfers, are considered in the model.

Given the complexity of the model, standard solvers such as CPLEX struggle even with small instances. To solve larger instances involving more modules and passenger requests, a two-phase heuristic is proposed. In the first phase, an initial feasible solution is generated by determining routing and passenger assignment decisions through a simplified DARP. The second phase employs a Large Neighborhood Search procedure to iteratively refine the solution, optimizing passenger transfers and module coupling and decoupling operations.

The proposed approach is evaluated on both synthetic and real-world-inspired networks across various operational scenarios, including human-driven and fully autonomous vehicle configurations. Computational experiments compare the performance of the two-phase heuristic with that of the MILP formulation solved using CPLEX, assessing key performance indicators including cost, service level, and capacity utilization. Results indicate that the method achieves a good balance between solution quality and computational efficiency. They also highlight the potential of modular transit systems to improve service quality and operational performance in dynamic mobility environments.

References

1. Filippi, C., Guastaroba, G., Peirano, L., and Speranza, M. G. (2025). Exploiting the flexibility of modular buses in an urban transit system. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 175. doi: 10.1016/j.trc.2025.105119.
2. Wu, J., Kulcsár, B., Selpi, and Qu, X. (2021). A modular, adaptive, and autonomous transit system (MAATS): An in-motion transfer strategy and performance evaluation in urban grid transit networks. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 151:81–98. doi: 10.1016/j.tra.2021.07.005.
3. Fu, Z. and Chow, J. Y. J. (2023). Dial-a-ride problem with modular platooning and enroute transfers. *Transportation Research Part C*, 152:104191. doi: 10.1016/j.trc.2023.104191.

PRODUCTION RESCHEDULING BASED ON MULTI-AGENT AUCTIONS

M. Gutierrez¹[0000-0002-9677-6764], J. Ordieres-Meré¹[0000-0002-9677-6764], E. Sirovnik² and C. Nölle³

¹ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

² Thyssenkrupp Rasselstein GmbH, Andernach, Germany

³ VDEh-Betriebsforschungsinstitut, Düsseldorf, Germany
miguel.gutierrez@upm.es

Keywords: Agent-Based Scheduling, Rescheduling, Flat Steel Parallel Lines.

In this work, we describe a scheduling system specifically designed to address the challenges of real-time reactive rescheduling in complex industrial settings like flat steel finishing. In such environments, traditional centralized optimization methods often fail to provide rapid solutions when faced with disruptions like equipment failures or unexpected order changes. To solve this, the research introduces a distributed multi-agent architecture that utilizes an auction-based allocation mechanism to enable fast and flexible decision-making [1-2].

At the conceptual level, the system models the production environment as a set of autonomous agents that represent the key operational entities involved in scheduling. Two main types of agents participate in the decision process: material agents, representing the coils or jobs that must be processed, and equipment agents, representing the available production units or finishing lines. In addition, a log or coordination agent records the events generated during the scheduling process and manages the initialization of auction rounds. This distributed representation allows decision-making responsibilities to be shared among agents rather than handled by a single centralized optimizer. The scheduling mechanism itself is based on iterative auctions between equipment and material agents.

During an auction, material agents evaluate their potential assignment to a specific piece of equipment by considering factors such as order priorities, due dates, and technological compatibility. They then submit a bid value reflecting the benefit of being processed next on that machine. The equipment agent evaluates these bids by estimating the processing costs, which include setup adjustments like width changes. By calculating a utility value—the difference between the material’s bid and the equipment’s processing cost—the agent selects the material that yields the highest overall value.

To ensure consistency across the distributed system, a confirmation step is required because material agents might participate in multiple auctions at once. Once a winner confirms its availability, it notifies other agents that it has been allocated, and the equipment agent fixes that material in its sequence before starting a new round for the next position. This iterative process continues until all materials are assigned, resulting in updated processing sequences that balance various objectives like delivery performance and setup efficiency [3].

Fig. 1. Multi-agent auction system architecture.

From an implementation perspective, the system relies on a distributed messaging infrastructure to ensure the rapid exchange of information among agents. The communication layer is built using Apache Kafka [4], which provides high-throughput event streaming and supports the large number of messages generated during the auction cycles. Fig. 1 represents the general architecture of the system.

Overall, the proposed auction-based multi-agent system provides a scalable and flexible framework for real-time reactive scheduling. By decentralizing decision making and enabling autonomous negotiation among agents, the system can rapidly adapt production schedules in response to disruptions while accommodating diverse operational rules and objectives.

Acknowledgments. This study is a result of the Project co-funded by the Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) G.A. 101112421.

References

- Cowling, P.I., Ouelhadj, D., Petrovic, S.: A multi-agent architecture for dynamic scheduling of steel hot rolling. *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing* 14, 457–470 (2003). doi.org/10.1023/A:1025701325275.
- Kumar, V., Kumar, S., Tiwari, M.K., Chan, F.T.S.: Auction-based approach to resolve the scheduling problem in the steel making process. *International Journal of Production Research* 44(8), 1503–1522 (2006). doi.org/10.1080/00207540500434713.
- Avni, G., Mallik, K., Sadhukhan, S.: Auction-Based Scheduling. *TACAS 2024, LNCS*, 14572, pp. 153-172. Springer, Cham. (2024). doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-57256-2_8.
- Narayanan, P.K.: Engineering Real-time Data Pipelines using Apache Kafka. In: *Data Engineering for Machine Learning Pipelines*. Apress, Berkeley, CA. (2024). doi.org/10.1007/979-8-8688-0602-5_9.

SCHEDULING RECOMMENDER SYSTEM FOR STEEL PRODUCTION

M. Gutierrez¹[0000-0002-9677-6764], J. Ordieres-Meré¹[0000-0002-9677-6764], E. Sirovnik² and C. Nölle³

¹ Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

² Thyssenkrupp Rasselstein GmbH, Andernach, Germany

³ VDEh-Betriebsforschungsinstitut, Düsseldorf, Germany
miguel.gutierrez@upm.es

Keywords: Steel Production Control, Scheduling Monitoring, Rescheduling.

In highly dynamic industrial environments, particularly in process industries such as steel finishing, production scheduling remains a critical yet challenging task due to frequent disruptions, tight operational constraints, and the need to balance efficiency with responsiveness. Traditional scheduling approaches, often reactive in nature, struggle to systematically exploit emerging improvement opportunities in real time. In this context, the integration of data-driven monitoring and intelligent rescheduling mechanisms offers significant potential to enhance decision-making [1, 2]. In this work we propose a scheduling recommender system aiming to support production control through proactive, analytically grounded scheduling assessments and improvements. The recommender system is conceptualized as depicted in Figure 1 and described as follows:

Intelligent Planning Monitoring System (IPMS). It is the core of the recommender system and the main component to develop specifically. It is aimed at identifying the opportunity to provide a relevant new schedule to the production manager. It encompasses two modules:

- The Performance Assessment Module (PAM). It interacts with real-time data. Periodically, it checks the suitability of the current schedule, identifying possible parameters in the equipments that might prevent the materials from being processed or that might lead to undesirable costs, or directly trigger the rescheduler to explore if a new schedule would yield relevant improvements. One way or the other is the module responsible for triggering the multiagent scheduler.
- Reschedule Assessment Module (RAM). From the results yield by the rescheduler it assesses both feasibility issues as well as possible improvements with respect to the current schedule. Then, according to some criteria, it must decide the interest in notifying the production manager.

In the case the Reschedule Assessment Module finds that the production manager should be notified regarding the interest of the new schedule, there is a need to send the production manager an assessment report and a file exportable to the information system (MES and/or proprietary), so she/he can decide if the proposal is of interest to be put into practice.

Plant Performance Models. Their role is to enable the consideration of highly dynamic, plant-specific information in the planning process, hence they interact with real-time equipment data. These components might work as independent modules of a production planning and control system, yet from the viewpoint of a generic design of a Recommender system, conceptually they would be included as a part of the Intelligent Planning Monitoring System.

Rescheduler. It has to ensure the possibility of attending both reactive and proactive demands [3]. Should a recommender system be developed from scratch or sold as an independent component, it would necessarily need to include a rescheduler module capable of dealing with real-time specificities.

Fig. 2. Recommender system conceptualization.

Acknowledgments. This study is a result of the Project co-funded by the Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) G.A. 101112421.

References

- Storck J., Lindberg B.: Assessment of Best Scheduling Practice in Continuous Casting and Hot Rolling of Stainless Steel Strip by System Dynamics Simulation. *Key Engineering Materials* 344, 897–904 (2007). doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/KEM.344.897
- Tang, L., Liu, J., Rong, A., Yang, Z.: A review of planning and scheduling systems and methods for integrated steel production. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 133 (1), 1-20 (2001). doi.org/10.1016/S0377-2217(00)00240-X.
- Uhlmann, I.R., Frazzon, E.M.: Production rescheduling review: Opportunities for industrial integration and practical applications. *Journal of Manufacturing Systems* 49, 186-193 (2018). doi.org/10.1016/j.jmsy.2018.10.004.

ID 4

HOW AI TOOLKIT SOLUTIONS ARE DISRUPTING GO-TO-MARKET STRATEGIES AND STREAMLINING BRAND DEVELOPMENT

Casimiro, G.

Abstract

As the digital economy shifts from algorithm-based discovery to intent-based automation, Generative AI (GenAI) is fundamentally restructuring traditional Go-to-Market (GTM) strategies. This paper explores the transition from static, linear sales funnels to dynamic, agentic commerce ecosystems where AI toolkits serve as both brand architects and active commercial conduits. Through a comparative case study analysis, this research highlights three distinct modalities of disruption: visual democratization, through tools such as GeneraAI and Lookbook AI; value transparency, embodied by Phia, an AI-powered shopping agent; and agentic commerce, exemplified by the Shopify integration within ChatGPT. Collectively, these examples demonstrate that the future of GTM strategy is not about managing traffic, but about optimizing for AI agents while delivering hyper-personalized value in real time.

ID 6

EVALUATING THE PERFORMANCE OF OSCILLATOR NETWORKS WITH A COMPREHENSIVE SUITE OF SYNCHRONIZATION METRICS

Dhamo, X.¹, Kalluci, E.¹, Xhafa, F.²¹Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Tirana, Albania²Department of Computer Science, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Spain

Abstract

Synchronization dynamics in oscillator networks is central to many natural and engineered systems, requiring robust methods for evaluating their performance. Building on our recent work on synchronization suppression using a hybrid Kuramoto–PPO model in fNIRS visibility networks, this article introduces an extended evaluation framework based on a comprehensive suite of synchronization metrics. We extend the study, which considered the synchronization suppression coefficient, by a suite of metrics comprising temporal, spectral, information-theoretic, stability-based, and network-level measures to capture complementary aspects of network behavior. Using visibility networks derived from fNIRS time-series data, we apply external control signals generated by the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm to a random subset of pinned nodes. The PPO component incorporates a cosine annealing learning-rate schedule to improve convergence properties. Large-scale experiments are executed on a Cluster computing infrastructure to guarantee statistical significance and consistency across multiple runs. A full comparative analysis of all metrics is performed to assess their ability to characterize synchronization performance, leading to a ranking based on sensitivity and discriminative power. Results showed that the suite of metrics provides a more complete and reliable assessment of oscillator network dynamics than single-measure approaches and enabled ranking the metrics according to their performance in the KM + PPO model.

ID 8

MODELING AND LINEARIZATION ANALYSIS OF A TOTAL ENERGY MINLP FOR SINGLE-TRUCK, MULTIPLE-DRONE LAST MILE DELIVERY

Xhafa, F.¹, Kalluci, E.², Gordani, O.²¹Department of Computer Science, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Spain²Faculty of Natural Sciences, University of Tirana, Albania

Abstract

Last-mile drone delivery continues to attract interest in logistics for faster, greener, and more cost-effective delivery solutions. In particular, single-truck, multiple-drone delivery systems offer substantial operational benefits but remain mathematically challenging to optimize due to the nonlinear nature of drone energy consumption and the uncertainties of battery usage. Previous studies have utilized simplified energy constraints involving only payload and distance, but real-world drone operations are governed by aerodynamics and propulsion dynamics requiring Total Energy Models. This paper proposes a Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) formulation for a comprehensive Total Energy Model that accounts for quadratic payload, cubic aerodynamic drag, bilinear ascent/descent power, and reciprocal speed-time coupling. Furthermore, we provide a theoretical derivation of a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) reformulation, analyzing tailored linearization schemes—such as piecewise linear approximations and McCormick envelopes—to address the non-convex constraints. Computational experiments on standard benchmark instances, extended here to the total energy function, evaluate the exact MINLP via the SCIP solver. The results demonstrate the feasibility of the exact nonlinear model for instances up to 45 customers and identify a “complexity wall” for larger instances. These findings confirm the need for rigorous energy modeling and establish a baseline for future computational studies of the proposed linear reformulations.

ID 9

FROM PORTFOLIO OPTIMIZATION TO STRUCTURAL DECISION-MAKING: A STRUCTURAL HEURISTIC THEORY OF CLIDUCTS, EVIDENCE FROM LARGE COMPANIES

Torrecilla, C., Lopez-Lopez, D.

Abstract

Product and customer portfolio decision-making is commonly supported by optimization models and managerial frameworks designed to maximize profitability, efficiency, or growth. Despite their widespread adoption, many organizations continue to experience systemic fragility, suggesting that these approaches overlook critical structural dimensions of portfolio performance. This paper examines the limitations of dominant portfolio decision frameworks and argues that portfolio failures often arise from structural blind spots rather than from poor execution or insufficient data. Building on a review of portfolio optimization and heuristic decision-making literature, the study analyzes the structural limitations of widely used managerial tools and conducts a longitudinal empirical analysis of large firms, including a comparative study of Microsoft and Apple over the period 2000–2025. Additional cross-industry case studies further illustrate how customer and product portfolio decisions can generate markedly different systemic outcomes. Based on this evidence, the paper introduces the Theory of Cliducts, a multidimensional framework that shifts the unit of analysis to the intersection of products and customer segments. The framework is proposed as a conceptual and integrative lens to interpret observed portfolio dynamics, conceptualizing portfolio quality as a problem of systemic balance between risk absorption, profitability generation, and reputational sustainability, rather than as the optimization of individual margins. The findings contribute to research on portfolio decision-making and customer portfolio management by offering an integrative perspective that aligns analytical rigor with observed organizational resilience under uncertainty.

ID 10

PHYSIOLOGICAL MARKERS AND THEIR IMPACT
ON DECISION-MAKING PERFORMANCE IN HIGH-
STAKES COMMERCIAL AVIATIONBelloni, G.^{1,2}, Aiello, F. A.³, Curşeu, P. L.^{4,5}¹Faculty of management, Open Universiteit, Heerlen, The Netherlands²HUMAI Research FZC, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates³Math Biology srl, Rome, Italy⁴Department of Organization, Open Universiteit, Heerlen, The Netherlands;⁵Department of Psychology, Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca, Romania

Abstract

Objectives: This review aims to identify non-invasive physiological signals for monitoring pilots' cognitive workload and stress in real time, and to evaluate how these signals can support safer behaviours and more effective decision-making in commercial aviation. **Background:** Pilots operate in highly complex socio-technical contexts where excessive cognitive load and stress can impair behaviours, situational awareness, decision-making, and performance, particularly during high-demand and abnormal operations. Real-time assessment of cognitive state is critical for preventing performance degradation and human-factor-related errors. **Methods:** A structured literature review was conducted using Google Scholar, Scopus, and PubMed. The initial search targeted studies on commercial airline pilots using predefined keyword combinations related to cognitive workload, stress, decision-making, and physiological monitoring. Given the limited availability of aviation-specific evidence, the search was subsequently expanded through a structured backwards and forward reference screening process to include other relevant studies from high-risk domains characterised by similar cognitive and operational demands. Studies were analysed in terms of physiological signals utilised, their reliability in detecting cognitive workload and stress, and their operational applicability to commercial aviation. **Results:** The reviewed literature suggests that some physiological and neurophysiological measures may help identify real-time variations in mental workload, stress, and cognitive functioning relevant to safer behaviours and more effective decision-making. Multimodal approaches appear to offer greater sensitivity and contextual robustness than single indicators, although

most available evidence remains derived from experimental or simulated settings with limited ecological validity. Conclusions: Real-time cognitive monitoring shows strong potential to support safer behaviours and decision-making, and to enhance effectiveness in increasingly complex aviation systems. However, practical implementation remains limited, underscoring the need for pilot-centred, non-intrusive solutions and ecologically valid research conducted in close collaboration with professional pilots.

ID 11

OPERATIONALIZING HUMAN-AI COLLABORATION FOR HIGH-VOLUME PROJECT RISK MANAGEMENT

Bara, M.^{1,2}

¹ICSO Analytics, Barcelona, Spain

²ESADE Business School, Barcelona, Spain

Abstract

Artificial intelligence tools can now generate hundreds of potential risk scenarios per project, creating an “intelligence paradox” where AI’s analytical power overwhelms rather than assists project managers. In previous work, we identified four human-AI collaboration patterns from cybersecurity, security screening, financial systems, and robotics that address high-volume risk management, and proposed a theoretical transfer framework to project management. However, that framework remained at the conceptual level, leaving a critical gap between theory and implementation. This paper operationalizes the framework into SHARP (Semantic Human-AI Risk Prioritization), defining: (a) a semantic triage system where AI classifies risks through contextual understanding rather than traditional probability-impact matrices, (b) a three-tier collaboration model (MONITOR/FLAG/ESCALATE) with clearly delineated AI and human responsibilities, and (c) a four-layer safety architecture ensuring the system fails safely when—not if—classification errors occur. We present an initial simulation-based evaluation using a synthetic project with planted ground-truth risks, processed through an LLM-based orchestration pipeline. The system is designed so that the project manager defines semantic classification rules while AI executes them at volume—preserving human judgment where it matters while delegating volume processing to AI.

ID 15

MULTIMODAL DIGITAL DECISION SUPPORT IN MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS: INTEGRATING REMOTE GAIT MONITORING AND MOBILE COGNITIVE ASSESSMENT FOR ECOLOGICALLY VALID DISEASE TRACKING

Farmanesh, A.¹, Ordieres-Meré, J.¹, Tabuenca, B.², Grijalvo, M.¹,
Díaz-Díaz, J.³, Aladro-Benito, Y.³

¹*Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales. Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, 28006 Madrid, Spain*

²*Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Sistemas Informáticos (ETSISI). Calle Alan Turing s/n, Carretera de Valencia, km 7, 28031 Madrid, Spain*

³*Hospital Universitario de Getafe, Unidad de Esclerosis Múltiple, 28905 Getafe, Spain*

Abstract

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic neurodegenerative disease characterized by progressive physical and cognitive impairment. Current clinical assessments are based on episodic clinic-based evaluations that provide limited ecological validity. Recent advances in mobile health and wearable technologies enable continuous monitoring of motor and cognitive function in real-world environments. This paper proposes an integrated digital decision-support framework that combines remote gait monitoring with mobile implementations of the Symbol Digit Modalities Test (SDMT) and Trail Making Test (TMT). Preliminary results from gait monitoring experiments and a large patient-centered survey demonstrate technical feasibility, discriminative sensitivity, and highlight adoption barriers. We discuss how multimodal digital biomarkers can enhance early detection, disease tracking, and personalized care in MS, while outlining limitations and future clinical validation pathways. These results should be interpreted as proof-of-concept due to the limited pilot sample size.

ID 16

A DECISION-SUPPORT-ORIENTED ECOSYSTEM BUSINESS MODEL FRAMEWORK FOR DIGITAL PRODUCT-SERVICE SYSTEMS

Blázquez, B.¹, Grijalvo, M.¹, Villalba-Díez, J.², Ordieres-Meré, J.¹

¹Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales. Universidad Politécnica de Madrid. José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, 28006 Madrid, Spain

²Fakultät für Wirtschaft, Hochschule Heilbronn, Bildungscampus, Max-Planck-Straße 39, Heilbronn, 74081 Germany

Abstract

Digital Product-Service Systems (PSS) increasingly rely on complex innovation ecosystems involving heterogeneous stakeholders and data-intensive infrastructures. While prior research has addressed value co-creation and servitization, limited attention has been paid to how ecosystem business models explicitly support multi-actor decision making. This paper proposes a decision-support-oriented framework for digital PSS ecosystems. Drawing on a structured literature review and multiple embedded case-based healthcare case-based models, we identify four archetypal ecosystem business models and introduce an integrative framework linking value creation, value capture, and data-driven decision loops. The results provide actionable information for managers and policymakers looking to design sustainable digital ecosystems.

ID 17

AHP-DRIVEN SUPPLIER SELECTION WITH AN APPLICATION TO THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

Lario, J.^{1,2}, Esteban Amaro, R.^{1,3}, Verdecho, M. J.^{1,2}*¹Departamento de Organización de Empresas, Universitat Politècnica de València,
España**²Centro de Investigación en Gestión e Ingeniería de Producción (CIGIP-UPV)**³Grupo de Investigación en Reingeniería, Organización, trabajo en Grupo y Logística
Empresarial – (ROGLE-UPV)*

Abstract

Supplier evaluation has become a strategic element in defining the competitiveness of manufacturing companies. The objective of this work is to provide future managers and decision-makers with a decision-making support model for supplier selection. This model is based on the Analytic Hierarchy Process and is applied to a case study in the automotive sector. The model begins by identifying fundamental criteria based on industry specific information. In the second phase of the proposed methodology, sub-criteria are created and prioritised using open-source software. Finally, an analysis is performed to evaluate which supplier best meets the selection criteria. The applied methodology offers a practical example of the various factors involved in supplier selection. Furthermore, the proposed approach facilitates prioritising evaluation criteria. This case study makes three original contributions to managerial decision sciences. First, it demonstrates how multi-criteria decision-making tools can support evidence-based supplier selection in real-world industrial environments. Secondly, the theoretical foundations are presented and then implemented by future engineers using open-source software. Finally, a simple application methodology is proposed to facilitate managers' identification and selection of the most suitable providers.

ID 18

FORECASTING RENEWABLE ENERGY PRODUCTION IN A MULTIREGIONAL FRAMEWORK

Guerra Ulloa, M.¹, Alonso, A. M.²

¹Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain

²Department of Statistics, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain

Abstract

This paper addresses the short-term forecasting of solar and wind energy electricity generation in the 12 administrative regions of France. In the scope of a multi-regional framework, the study explores and compares Machine Learning and Deep Learning approaches, including XGBoost, LSTM, and hybrid CNN-GRU neural networks. Hourly data spanning 2018 to 2022, including meteorological variables and historical production, are used to train and validate the model with data from 2018–2021, and to evaluate its performance using data from 2022. The methodology incorporates rolling-window forecasting and region-specific modeling to capture temporal dynamics and spatial heterogeneity. Forecast accuracy is evaluated using standard error metrics (MAE, RMSE, NRMSE) and the Diebold-Mariano test. Results highlight the superior performance of Machine Learning and Deep Learning models in capturing nonlinearities and temporal dependencies. Regions with higher energy production report lower error metrics.

ID 19

SOLVING A ROUTING PROBLEM WITHOUT A ROUTING ALGORITHM: A CASE STUDY IN FOOD DISTRIBUTION

Capitano, D.¹, Distratis, G.¹, Righini, G.², Rossi, I.¹*¹KPMG Advisory SpA, Via G.B. Pirelli, 20124, Milan, Italy**²University of Milan, Department of Computer Science, Via Celoria 18, 20133, Milan, Italy*

Abstract

We illustrate a case study concerning distribution logistics for a large Italian company in the food supply chain. The underlying capacitated vehicle routing problem was indirectly solved as a heterogeneous bin packing problem, owing to the typically small number of destinations reached in each trip. This allowed obtaining reliable estimates of the potential savings without having recourse to specialized vehicle routing algorithms. Flexibility in space and time were introduced and evaluated, showing significant potential for cost reduction. Furthermore, the introduction of a mathematical model meant to replace or at least support manual planning allowed to explicitly minimize costs instead of relying upon a heuristic proxy like the saturation level of the chosen vehicles.

ID 20

GNN MIXTURE-OF-EXPERTS FOR SEGMENT- LEVEL TRAVEL TIME PREDICTION IN LAST-MILE DELIVERY

Amerehi, F.¹, Carroll, P.¹¹University College Dublin, Ireland

Abstract

Predicting travel time between consecutive delivery stops, segment-level travel time prediction (SLTTP), is critical for optimizing dispatch in last-mile courier operations. However, SLTTP remains challenging due to the heterogeneity of delivery routes, as urban and suburban environments exhibit substantially different traffic patterns and route complexities. While graph neural networks (GNNs) capture inter-segment relationships, they apply a single set of parameters across all segments, which may not fully account for varying levels of route difficulty. In this work, we study whether a mixture-of-experts (MoE) architecture with difficulty-aware specialization can address this imbalance. In particular, we focus on two design aspects: (i) the gating strategy, comparing fixed difficulty-based gating to learned soft gating, and (ii) the scope of expert training, contrasting joint training with stratification across difficulty groups. We evaluate five models, spanning gradient-boosted machines (GBM) and graph attention networks (GAT), on 1.17 million real-world delivery segments. Our findings indicate that GAT models outperform GBM baselines by 8–14%, especially on medium and high difficulty segments. We observe that fixed gating yields more stable expert assignments, while stratified training further improves performance, together yielding the best overall model.

ID 22

CLUSTERING UNIVERSITY DROPOUT PROFILES: A COMPARISON OF UNSUPERVISED METHODS FOLLOWING PCA AND UMAP PREPROCESSING ON STEM STUDENTS

Talens-Cogollos, A.¹, Maheut, J.², Igualde-Sáez, A.²¹Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022, Valencia, Spain²ROGLE, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022, Valencia, Spain

Abstract

Higher education institutions hold substantial academic and sociodemographic data on their students, which can be leveraged to improve institutional efficiency and student outcomes. Whilst machine learning approaches to university dropout have predominantly focused on prediction, fewer studies seek to understand the underlying factors through unsupervised methods. This paper applies clustering techniques to identify dropout profiles, aiming to comprehend the causes and unmet needs of students who withdraw. Using an open-access dataset from Universitat Politècnica de València containing sociodemographic variables from STEM student enrolments (2018-2023), we compared the performance of K-means, Ward's hierarchical clustering, Gaussian mixture models, and Partitioning around medoids. Following data preprocessing and dimensionality reduction via Principal Component Analysis and Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection, six distinct dropout profiles emerged. Results indicate that K-means and Partitioning Around Medoids achieved the highest performance (Silhouette: 0.65 and Davies-Bouldin: 0.41), identifying six distinct profiles that reveal a fundamental distinction between early-stage disengagement and late-stage withdrawal linked to labour market entry.

ID 23

EBUDDY: A WORKFLOW ORCHESTRATOR FOR INDUSTRIAL HUMAN-MACHINE COLLABORATION

Banfi, M.¹, Felici, R.¹, Baraldo, S.¹, Avram, O.¹, Valente, A.¹*¹Laboratory of Automation, Robotics and Machines (ARM), University of Applied
Sciences of Southern Switzerland, Lugano-Viganello, Switzerland*

Abstract

This paper presents EBuddy, a voice-guided workflow orchestrator for natural human-machine collaboration in industrial environments. EBuddy targets a recurrent bottleneck in tool-intensive workflows: expert know-how is effective but difficult to scale, and execution quality degrades when procedures are reconstructed ad hoc across operators and sessions. EBuddy operationalizes expert practice as a Finite State Machine (FSM) driven application that provides an interpretable decision frame at runtime (current state and admissible actions), so that spoken requests are interpreted within state-grounded constraints, while the system executes and monitors the corresponding tool interactions. Through modular workflow artifacts, EBuddy coordinates heterogeneous resources, including GUI-driven software and a collaborative robot, leveraging fully voice-based interaction through automatic speech recognition and intent understanding. An industrial pilot on impeller blade inspection and repair preparation for Directed Energy Deposition (DED), realized by human-robot collaboration, shows substantial reductions in end-to-end process duration across onboarding, 3D scanning and processing, and repair program generation, while preserving repeatability and low operator burden.

ID 25

GRAPH-BASED RETRIEVAL-AUGMENTED PLANNING FOR ROBOTS WITH PROVENANCE- AWARE KNOWLEDGE

Leanza, A.¹, Roveda, L.^{1,2}, Spahiu, B.³

¹Department of Innovative Technologies (DTI), Dalle Molle Institute for Artificial Intelligence (IDSIA), University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI), 6900 Lugano, Ticino, Switzerland

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Politecnico di Milano, 20156 Milano, Italy

³Department of Informatics, Systems and Communication (DISCO), University of Milano-Bicocca, 20126 Milano, Italy

Abstract

Large Language Models (LLMs) can decompose natural language instructions into high-level robot subgoals, but in embodied settings they often produce ungrounded plans—hallucinating tools/actions, referencing unavailable objects, or making unsafe assumptions under underspecified requests. We propose a fully local, graph-based retrieval-augmented planning framework that grounds task decomposition in a persistent, object-centric knowledge graph with provenance. For each perceived object, the system ingests scene-associated documents (Wikipedia in our prototype, manuals, user notes) and uses a local LLM to extract schema-constrained triples from a fixed predicate vocabulary (e.g., MADE_OF, USED_FOR, HAS_TOXICITY), storing each fact with confidence, source metadata, and links to supporting evidence chunks. At planning time, we retrieve a scene-conditioned candidate pool and select a compact, diverse subset under a prompt budget using reliability- and relevance-aware scoring, then condition a local LLM to output a grounded JSON subgoal sequence with restricted action templates. Experiments on the ConceptBot task suite show that provenance-linked graph retrieval improves grounding and safety-related decisions over SayCan and a ConceptBot w/o ConceptNet ablation, and is competitive with full ConceptBot while surpassing it on attribute-centric Materials and Toxicity tasks.

ID 26

HUMAN-LLM COLLABORATIVE DECISION- MAKING FOR MANUFACTURING DISRUPTION MANAGEMENT IN INDUSTRY 5.0

Kiangala, K. S.¹, Wang, Z.¹

¹*Department of Electrical and Smart Systems Engineering, University of South Africa
(UNISA), Johannesburg, 1709, Gauteng, South Africa*

Abstract

Manufacturing disruption management involves complex decisions that require balancing competing objectives such as production delay, energy consumption, product quality, and operational safety. While recent advances in artificial intelligence (AI) enable accurate failure predictions and anomalies, translating predictive insights into actionable and trustworthy decisions remains a challenge in real-world industrial settings. Fully automated approaches often lack transparency in decision-making, and less automated ones, which mainly rely on human validation, can suffer from inconsistency in multi-criteria trade-offs. This paper proposes a human-LLM collaborative decision framework for manufacturing disruption management in Industry 5.0 environments. The framework integrates predictive analytics for disruption detection, a structured multi-criteria decision model for evaluating recovery actions, and a large language model (LLM) that operates as a reasoning and explanation agent. Rather than autonomously selecting actions, the LLM generates natural-language explanations of trade-offs to support human validation, transparency, and control. We evaluate the framework using both synthetic disruption scenarios and real-world predictive maintenance data from the AI4I 2020 dataset. Synthetic experiments demonstrate strong alignment between human-only and automated decisions, with agreement rates exceeding 95%, while highlighting increased human variability in high-conflict scenarios involving competing objectives. Real-world experiments show clear risk-sensitive decision behavior, with recovery strategies shifting from continuity-preserving actions under negligible predicted failure risk to conservative interventions under high risk. The results provide practical evidence that human-LLM collaboration improve consistency, interpretability, and confidence in manufacturing disruption management. The proposed

framework bridges predictive intelligence and operational decision-making as it offers a human-centric practical decision-support approach aligned with Industry 5.0 principles.

ID 27

A LOCAL-SEARCH-ENHANCED ITERATED GREEDY ALGORITHM FOR THE RANK PRICING PROBLEM WITH TIES

Calvete, H. I.¹, Galé, C.¹, Hernández, A.¹, Iranzo, J. A.¹

¹Departamento de Métodos Estadísticos, Instituto Universitario de Investigación en Matemáticas y Aplicaciones (IUMA), Universidad de Zaragoza, Pedro Cerbuna 12, Zaragoza 50009, Spain

Abstract

The Rank Pricing Problem with Ties is an optimization problem in which a company sets product prices to maximize revenue, while each customer purchases at most one affordable item according to a ranked list of products that may contain ties. In case of indifference among several products in terms of preference, the natural behavior of the customers consists in selecting the cheapest one, which requires adopting the pessimistic approach when the problem is modeled as a bilevel optimization problem. This paper proposes a local-search-enhanced iterated greedy algorithm for solving the problem. The method exploits the discrete structure of candidate prices, alternating destruction–construction steps, with an efficient evaluation of customer reactions that explicitly accounts for their purchasing behavior. Computational experiments are conducted on both a newly generated test set and benchmark instances from the literature. The results show that the proposed algorithm consistently delivers high-quality solutions within competitive computing times, providing an effective alternative when exact methods become computationally demanding.

ID 28

FROM PLANNING TO AGENTS: HOW ROBUST ARE LLM-GENERATED HEURISTICS?

Chen, W.¹, Conejero, J. A.²

¹*CIGIP-ValgrAI, Universitat Politècnica de València, Plaza de Ferrándiz y Carbonell
s/n, Alcoy, 03801, Spain*

²*Instituto Universitario de Matemática Pura y Aplicada, Universitat Politècnica de
València, Camí de Vera s/n, Valencia, 46022, Spain*

Abstract

Recently, large language models (LLMs) have been used to automatically generate heuristic functions for classical planning. While early results indicate that such heuristics can be competitive with established baselines, their evaluation is typically limited to a single search algorithm, leaving questions about robustness across different search dynamics. In classical planning, however, heuristic effectiveness is closely tied to the search strategy in which the heuristic is embedded. We present a systematic analysis of heuristics generated by a single LLM configuration, Gemini 2.5 Flash, across multiple heuristic-driven search algorithms. Rather than assessing performance in isolation, we examine how the same heuristic behaves under Greedy Best-First Search, A*, and Weighted A*. Our evaluation considers three complementary dimensions: coverage, search efficiency, and solution quality. All experiments are conducted on the Blocksworld domain from the IPC 2023 Learning Track, using the FF heuristic as a reference baseline. The results show that LLM-generated heuristics exhibit heterogeneous behavior. Some heuristics are highly sensitive to search dynamics, while others perform robustly across search algorithms, achieving consistent coverage and strong search efficiency without sacrificing solution quality. These findings underscore the importance of evaluating LLM-generated heuristics beyond single-algorithm settings and help clarify the properties that distinguish robust heuristics from search-dependent ones in classical planning.

ID 30

AI DECISION-SUPPORT FOR ETHICAL CONTEXTS: INSIGHTS FROM WILDLIFE MANAGEMENT AND IMPLICATIONS FOR BUSINESS

López López, D.¹, Martín Méndez, A.²*¹ESADE Business School Barcelona**²Universidad Europea de Madrid (UEM), Facultad de Ciencias Biomédicas y de la Salud (Madrid)*

Abstract

Evidence-based wildlife management often confronts ethical conflicts: field measurements can inform decisions, but they cannot resolve clashes of values, such as whether protecting biodiversity justifies human intervention. This study proposes an AI-supported framework for the transparent management of ethical conflict in wildlife decision-making. The framework adopts a constraint-first structure in which ethical principles are translated into non-negotiable constraints that define the feasible set of interventions, while remaining objectives are evaluated transparently within those limits. It integrates stakeholder mapping, the specification of ethical barriers and objectives, the explicit structuring of evidence and uncertainty, the comparison of feasible policy alternatives, and the definition of monitoring indicators and decision triggers for adaptive management. AI is positioned as a bounded decision-support tool that helps process information, document reasoning, clarify assumptions, and improve traceability, rather than serving as an automated decision-maker on ethical questions. The paper illustrates the framework through a wildlife conflict case, showing how it can support justifiable intervention decisions under uncertainty while making trade-offs, implementation requirements, and governance safeguards explicit. The approach also has broader relevance for business and organisational decision-making contexts characterised by ethical constraints, competing objectives, and uncertainty.

ID 31

DESIGN AND OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING IN A DUAL-DEGRADATION ASSET HEALTH INDEX MODEL FOR POWER TRANSFORMERS

Crespo-Márquez, A.¹, Sánchez-Herguedas, A.¹, Carballo-
Menayo, A.¹, Romero-Sánchez, P.¹, Paloma-Castro, E.¹

*¹Department of Industrial Management, School of Engineering, University of Seville,
Spain*

Abstract

This paper proposes a Dual-Degradation Asset Health Index (DD-AHI) model for power transformers that explicitly separates non-recoverable degradation (NRD) from recoverable degradation (RD) within a probabilistic reliability framework. Unlike conventional composite health indices, the DD-AHI defines health as the complement of the probability of at least one failure over a one-year interval, enabling direct integration with reliability theory and decision analysis. The model combines Weibull baseline reliability, Non-Homogeneous Poisson Process (NHPP) discretisation, and Cox proportional hazards modelling to dynamically adjust the failure intensity based on covariates defined condition-monitoring variables. Beyond its mathematical formulation, the DD-AHI is conceptualised as a structured decision architecture. Model-design decisions—such as degradation classification, hazard envelope definition, and parameter calibration—encode risk assumptions, while operational outputs support maintenance optimisation, load management, fleet prioritisation, and replacement strategy. The framework contributes to Decision Science by formalising the feedback loop between modelling assumptions and asset-management decisions in critical energy infrastructure.

ID 32

FROM DOCUMENTATION TO PROCESS-CENTRIC DECISION-MAKING: DEPLOYING THE PIPES AND PUDDLES FRAMEWORK ON THE GRAPHIC ARTS SHOP FLOOR OF A SUPPORTED EMPLOYMENT CENTER

García-Gerbolés, C.¹, Valdés López-Linares, I.¹, Costas-Gual,
J.², Gutiérrez, M.¹

*¹Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales, Universidad Politécnica de
Madrid. Calle de José Gutiérrez Abascal 2 28006, Madrid, Spain*

*²Grupo de Ingeniería de Organización, Universidad de Oviedo. Campus de Viesques
s/n 33204, Gijón, Spain*

Abstract

The process-centric approach in organizations is increasingly widespread, even becoming an indispensable requirement in some sectors. However, the literature points out that there is a gap between the quality standards that require this approach and their tangible effects on decision-making. Pipes and Puddles is a management framework that seeks to precisely avoid this gap and provide a roadmap for decision-making so that this process-centric approach becomes normal operating practice in organizations. This paper presents and analyzes the first attempt in the literature to apply this framework in a real organization. The organization that serves as the use case in our work is a supported employment center for people with disabilities in the graphic arts sector of Spain. The project was conducted in collaboration with Alex Rivera Foundation. The framework deployment includes the development of an overall process map, turtle diagrams, detailed flowcharts, and cognitively accessible work instructions to support inter- and intra-process standards across different operational layers and processes within the organization. Although the implementation had a limited scope, the results show measurable outcomes such as a reduction in inventory discrepancies and a reduction in employee training time. Mapping and implementing standards across the organization helped increase its level of maturity and highlighted the

usefulness of standards and the process-centric approach beyond a mere documentary exercise.

ID 34

THE IMPACT OF DATA PREPROCESSING ON STUDENT DROPOUT PREDICTION: A COMPARATIVE STUDY AT A SPANISH TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY

Igualde-Sáez, A.¹, Maheut, J.¹, Talens-Cogollos, A.², García-Sabater, J. P.¹

¹ROGLE Departamento de Organización de Empresas, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 Valencia, Spain

²Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022 Valencia, Spain

Abstract

Student dropout prediction through machine learning has gained significant attention. However, limited research has examined the effect of data preprocessing on model performance and interpretability. This study presents a comparative analysis of two approaches at a large Spanish technological university with predominantly in-person instruction. The first approach operates directly on raw, subject-level data with minimal preprocessing, whereas the second implements a systematic pipeline that aggregates at the student level. Three academic cohorts (2018-2019, 2021-2022, 2022-2023) are analysed, comprising approximately 465,000 records from 39,364 students. The baseline approach achieves AUC of up to 0.99, but this result is inflated by row-level splitting that places the same student's records in both training and test sets. Under rigorous evaluation without such data leakage, the proposed pipeline achieves an AUC of 0.77. Both approaches exhibit significant degradation across COVID-19 cohort boundaries (AUC drops to 0.58--0.70). These findings highlight that preprocessing decisions shape reported performance more than algorithm selection.

ID 35

FRAMEWORK FOR DEFINING FUTURE RESEARCH LINES ON SUSTAINABILITY-DRIVEN AI IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR

Martínez-Pastor, A.¹, Sanchis, R.¹, Poler, R.¹

¹Research Centre on Production Management and Engineering, Universitat Politècnica de València, Plaza de Ferrándiz y Carbonell s/n, 03801 Alcoy (Alicante), España

Abstract

The construction sector faces growing environmental and operational challenges that require integrated approaches to improve sustainability across the building lifecycle. Artificial Intelligence, optimisation methods, Multi-Criteria Decision-Making, and Life Cycle Assessment have been increasingly applied to address these challenges; however, research remains fragmented. This study identifies the future research directions in the literature and proposes a structured framework to guide further investigations. A systematic review was conducted using the CIMO framework and Scopus as the primary database, resulting in 23 selected review articles. Thematic and content analyses were performed to examine lifecycle coverage, methodological trends, and research priorities. The findings reveal a strong concentration on early design stages, with limited attention to operation, retrofitting, and component-level applications. In response, the study proposes a multi-layer framework, highlighting the interaction between computational intelligence, human expertise, and lifecycle-based evaluation. This framework provides a roadmap for advancing AI-driven sustainable construction by improving interoperability, system integration, and data-driven decision-making across lifecycle stages.

ID 36

HACKING MATHEMATICS: A STEAM CURRICULUM INTEGRATING MATHEMATICS, 3D FABRICATION AND IOT FOR SOCIETY 5.0

Fonseca Casas, M. C.¹, Fonseca Casas, P.²¹*Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Spain*²*Springer Heidelberg, Tiergartenstr. 17, 69121 Heidelberg, Germany*

Abstract

This paper presents Hacking Mathematics, a ten-session STEAM curriculum designed for the first year of upper secondary education. The curriculum integrates computational thinking, number systems, combinatorics and probability, list structures and automation, decision logic, descriptive statistics, and geometric design with hands on 3D modelling and Internet of Things (IoT) instrumentation. Organized as five paired guides (example model + autonomous laboratory guide), the sequence combines instructor demonstrations with step-by-step laboratory tasks using block-based programming, visual and parametric CAD, and a cloud-based IoT dashboard to link physical prototypes with real-time data. Practical constraints related to accessibility and material optimization are embedded throughout the activities, including tactile relief for buttons, parametric tolerances for press-fit mechanisms, and infill strategies that support sustainable additive manufacturing. A mixed-methods pilot with a single student cohort shows conceptual gains, strong procedural fluency in base conversions and modular programming, and sustained engagement with data driven iteration and inclusive design practices. The paper provides complete session plans, assessment rubrics, telemetry schemas, and teacher supports, and concludes with recommendations for classroom adoption, targeted professional development, and scalable deployment of integrated STEAM learning pathways.

ID 38

SOLVING ROUTING PROBLEMS WITH MULTIPLE DRONES WITH INTERCEPTIONS

Dillon, S.¹, Grobler, J.¹*¹Department of Industrial Engineering, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa*

Abstract

This paper uses two evolutionary algorithms and a swarm intelligence algorithm to solve the multiple drone delivery problem with interceptions. A differential evolution-based algorithm, a covariance matrix adaptation-evolution strategy, and a particle swarm optimisation-based algorithm are used to solve an adaptation of the travelling salesman problem with a drone with interceptions which allows for multiple drones on board the truck. Multiple drones can be launched to deliver packages while the truck delivers packages to customers. After completing a delivery, the drones are allowed to either meet the truck at the next customer location or intercept the purpose-built truck while the truck is en-route. The results show that the swarm intelligence algorithm with the nearest neighbour initialisation strategy is the best-performing algorithm when solving the travelling salesman problem with multiple drones with interception. This paper is the first to utilise continuous metaheuristic algorithms for solving the travelling salesman problem with multiple drones with interception.

ID 40

USING HIGH-RESOLUTION MODELING TO REDUCE BASIS RISK IN TROPICAL CYCLONE PARAMETRIC RISK TRANSFER STRUCTURES: A CASE STUDY

Lemke-Verderame, L.¹, Mudd, L.², Guidotti, R.¹, Franco, G.¹*¹Guy Carpenter & Company, LLC, 1166 Avenue of the Americas, New York, 10036,
NY, USA**²Applied Research Associates, Inc, 8537 Six Forks Rd, Suite 600, Raleigh, NC 27615,
USA*

Abstract

Parametric insurance is a form of risk transfer that triggers payouts according to measurable properties of an event (e.g. the maximum sustained wind speed of a hurricane within a pre-defined geographic region). While parametric insurance has many benefits including a quick and transparent procedure for the disbursement of funds, it carries “basis risk” which may be defined as the difference between the actual losses sustained and the parametric recovery. The design and assessment of parametric solutions requires extensive data sets, often derived from catastrophe risk models capable of estimating losses to an asset under many simulated events. In this paper, we investigate whether increasing the resolution of the model data used to calibrate parametric solutions would decrease their basis risk. We test two solutions designed to transfer tropical cyclone risk for an asset in Miami Beach, Florida. The first is calibrated based on outputs standard to most models (i.e. tropical cyclone track data and total event loss). The second is calibrated based on an enhanced data set which supplements the standard data with incremental losses incurred along the tropical cyclone track, allowing calibration using loss progression information at each reported track point. We find that the solution based on the enhanced data set decreases the basis risk by about 4%. This paper establishes a procedure to investigate the effect of the underlying model data on basis risk. We anticipate that additional case studies exhibiting similar or larger reductions in basis risk might encourage the expansion of outputs by standard catastrophe risk models.

ID 41

EXPLORING THE RANKINE VORTEX DYNAMICS USING CELLULAR AUTOMATA IN 2D COMPUTATIONAL FLUID DYNAMICS

Aliaoui, M.¹, Fonseca i Casas, P.¹¹*Polytechnic University of Catalonia, Spain*

Abstract

This work investigates the use of Cellular Automata (CA) as a discrete alternative to traditional methods reliant on the Navier-Stokes equations for simulating Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) in two dimensions. By focusing on the Rankine vortex, which is characterized by solid rotation in its core and a potential vortex outside, we evaluate the effectiveness of this approach in simulating real-world rotational phenomena such as hurricanes and turbine flows. The research involves developing a simulator in the C programming language based on local rules of CA interaction. We validate the results by comparing them with simulations from established commercial software, such as Autodesk CFD, while also analyzing computational efficiency in terms of calculation times. The foundational principles of the Rankine vortex are elucidated, including the tangential and angular velocity equations, alongside the unique characteristics of CAs for modeling physical systems, particularly m:n-CAk models that incorporate variables like velocity, density, and pressure. Preliminary results demonstrate that the CA model successfully reproduces vortex dynamics, offering an efficient alternative for 2D simulations at a reduced computational cost compared to continuous methods, albeit with some limitations in accuracy for viscous fluids. This bottom-up approach paves the way for innovative applications in aerodynamics, hydrodynamics, and meteorology, underscoring the significant potential of CAs within resource-constrained computational environments.

ID 44

PERCEPTION OF AI AND DIGITALIZATION IN THE SPANISH PIG SECTOR

Llagostera, P.^{1,2}, Font, P.^{1,2}, Sacanell, V. L.^{2,3}, Plà-Aragonés, L.
M.^{1,2}

¹Department of Mathematics, Universitat de Lleida, Lleida, Spain

²Agrotecnio-CERCA Center, Lleida, Spain

³Research Group in AgrolCT & Precision Agriculture (GRAP), Department of
Agricultural and Forest Sciences and Engineering (DCEFA), Universitat de Lleida,
Lleida, Spain

Abstract

Spain is a EU leader in pig production, a highly competitive sector, becoming an export-oriented industry in which the rapid diffusion of sensors, computer vision and farm management software is transforming production practices and decision-making. While digitalisation and artificial intelligence (AI) are promoted as levers to enhance efficiency, animal welfare and environmental performance, technology uptake remains uneven and shaped by farmers' perceptions, capabilities and concerns. This study, based on a survey of more than 300 respondents, investigates how different actors in the pig supply chain understand and evaluate AI-enabled and digital technologies, focusing on perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, data governance and their implications for work organisation and professional autonomy. Drawing on survey data collected from producers, integrators, veterinarians and technology providers at national level, we analyse drivers and barriers to adoption, including farm structure, digital skills, investment capacity and previous experience with automation. Our results point to a generally positive attitude towards AI-based monitoring and decision-support tools when they are transparent, job-relevant and demonstrably reliable, but also reveal persistent reservations linked to costs, data access, lack of explainability and fears of increased external control over farm management. These findings underline the need for participatory, user-centred innovation strategies and policy instruments that couple technical development with capacity building, fair data frameworks and governance mechanisms that recognise farmers as key co-designers of digital transformation in the pig sector.

ID 48

BLOCKCHAIN FRAUD DETECTION FOR EXPLAINABLE FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS

Trerotola, M.¹, Calvaresi, D.², Parente, M.³¹*Politecnico di Torino, Torino, Italy*²*University of Applied Sciences and Arts Western Switzerland (HES-SO), Sion,
Switzerland*³*Università degli Studi di Salerno, Salerno, Italy*

Abstract

In 2024, cryptocurrency-related fraud exceeded \$40 billion, challenging UN Sustainable Development Goal 16.4 on illicit financial flows. Existing methods face a recurring trade-off: deep models are accurate but opaque, while interpretable pipelines are often chain-specific. We propose an explainable graph-temporal Machine Learning framework whose methodology is reusable across heterogeneous ledgers by relying on chain-specific feature extractors, instantiated in this work on Bitcoin and Ethereum. The method combines architecture-neutral structural, monetary, and temporal features; Balanced Random Forests for severe class imbalance; and a three-layer XAI stack (SHAP, CIU, DEXiRE) for global, local, and symbolic auditing. ChainAbuse intelligence (15k+ reports) supports periodic retraining as fraud patterns evolve. Evaluated on 31,000 Bitcoin wallets and 157,000 Ethereum tokens, the framework achieves macro-F1 up to 0.92 and 0.985, respectively, while preserving full transparency.

ID 50

FAST, FAITHFUL, AND FAIR: REAL-TIME PROBABILISTIC XAI VIA KNOWLEDGE DISTILLATION

Garcia-Climent, E.¹, Serrat, C.¹, Belanche Muñoz, L.¹*¹Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain*

Abstract

Explainability (XAI) is a critical requirement in high-stakes decision-making systems such as credit scoring, particularly under emerging regulations like the EU AI Act. State-of-the-art methods like SHAP, while accurate, present computational costs that are prohibitive for real-time production environments. In this work, we present a Knowledge Distillation framework that transfers the interpretability of a complex teacher model (XGBoost) to a lightweight Probabilistic Neural Network (Student). Our results across three real-world financial datasets (Taiwan, German, and Bank Marketing) demonstrate a speedup of up to 9,800x (latency < 0.06 ms) while maintaining high explanatory fidelity ($R^2 > 0.78$). Additionally, we demonstrate how this framework enables real-time fairness auditing, detecting latent structural biases in historical data.

ID 52

AI MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR AUTONOMOUS DECISION- MAKING IN THE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY

Andres, B.¹, Poler, R.¹, Figueroa, A.¹, Garrido, N.²*¹Research Centre on Production Management and Engineering, Universitat
Politécnica de València, 46880 Valencia, Spain**²Instituto de Matemática Multidisciplinar, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022
Valencia, Spain*

Abstract

The growing development of Industry 4.0 has significantly increased the complexity of modern manufacturing systems, creating the need for more interoperable and scalable systems geared towards intelligent decision-making. The trend towards artificial intelligence (AI) in recent years has driven research into multi-agent systems (MAS), which have proven to be a suitable technology for modelling distributed and intelligent systems for autonomous decision-making. However, MAS still show practical limitations in real industry due to a lack of integration with essential industrial enablers, such as manufacturing execution systems (MES), production planning and control (PPC), and data-driven operations research (OR) approaches. Therefore, this work proposes an AI-based MAS conceptual framework for autonomous decision-making in the manufacturing industry, capable of transforming raw industrial data into viable, explainable, and autonomous decisions. The conceptual framework is structured in a multi-layer architecture that integrates data acquisition and management, an intelligent MAS-based core with integrated analytical capabilities, and a level of explainability and decision support that ensures transparency and human supervision.

ID 57

A MULTISTART HEURISTIC FOR 3D BIN PACKING AND ROUTING PROBLEM IN WAREHOUSE AUTOMATION

Guerrero Portoles, A.¹, López-Sánchez, A.¹, Cancio-Donlebún,
D.¹, García-Sánchez, A.²

¹*Baobab Soluciones, Madrid 28003, Spain*

²*Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid 28006, Spain*

Abstract

This study addresses the simultaneous optimization of a 3D Bin Packing and Routing Problem for the automated preparation of orders within a warehouse. The planning begins as soon as an order is received to optimize the picking workflow. In this environment, mobile robots navigate to specific item locations where human operators then place the goods onto the pallets carried by the robots. Since each robot carries only one pallet, the number of pallets utilized directly dictates the size of the robot fleet assigned to an order. The primary challenge is the tight coupling between the picking sequence and physical stability, since the order of collection directly determines the structural feasibility of the load. To manage this, the model integrates constraints including weight limits and a stacking hierarchy, making sturdier items support lighter ones. Dynamic constraints are also used to prevent the formation of unsupported structures during transit to keep the load secure at every individual step of the picking route.

Due to the large scale of the orders, which may contain hundreds or thousands of items, finding a global optimum is computationally infeasible. Therefore, a multistart heuristic was developed to determine pallet loading and picking routes under these constraints. Evaluation on real customer data shows the algorithm operates between five and ten times faster than the current operational planning system and increases pallet volume utilization, reducing the number of pallets and robots required per order. This reduction in pallets also decreases the logistical costs associated with downstream shipping. Additionally, the total distance traveled by the robot fleet was also reduced by nearly 50%, improving overall warehouse throughput.

ID 58

OPTIMIZATION OF ORDER BATCHING AND SCHEDULING WITH SOFT TIME-WINDOW DUE DATES

Jahed, A.¹, García-Sánchez, A.¹*¹Department of Industrial Engineering, Business Administration and Statistics, ETSII,
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain*

Abstract

Order batching and scheduling play a crucial role in warehouse operations, particularly when customer orders must be fulfilled within a specified time frame. Most previous studies on mathematical models and methods have focused on the order picking problem under a certain due date assumption, where tardiness is treated as a positive difference between an order completion time and its certain due date. However, in a real-world distribution setting, both earliness and tardiness of customer orders are evaluated with respect to their due windows. Hence, to address this gap, in this study a new multi-objective mathematical model is designed to distinguish this work from previous studies by considering the joint order batching and scheduling with soft time window due dates in a manual picker-to-parts system. Therefore, a comprehensive mixed integer linear programming (MILP) model is proposed to minimize completion time, earliness, and tardiness of customer orders, and maximize the utility of customers. Jointly addressing order batching and scheduling operations can improve the efficiency of customer service and operational cost. The proposed mathematical model effectively solves small and medium-scale instances up to 50 orders, which indicates the efficiency and applicability of the proposed model.

ID 67

INTERACTIVE ONLINE TOURIST ITINERARY RECOMMENDER WITH DYNAMIC OPTIMISATION

González Navasa, C.^{1,2}, Moreno Pérez, J.^{3,4}, Brito Santana,
J.^{3,4}, Alonso Afonso, H.^{2,3}

¹Dep. of Data Science, Atlantis Technology, 38206 La Laguna, Spain

²Dep. Informática y Sistemas, University of La Laguna, 38271 La Laguna, Spain

³Instituto Universitario de Desarrollo Regional, University of La Laguna

⁴Ph.D. Student, University of La Laguna, 38271 La Laguna, Spain

Abstract

This paper describes the architecture, methodologies, and technologies underlying the components of an interactive online tourist itinerary recommender. The core innovation of this proposal is on the interactive online module, which features a dynamic adaptive optimisation procedure based on metaheuristics. To be effective, an intelligent tourist trip recommender must adapt its recommendation to real-time changes in context and user requirements. An intelligent traveller recommender at the destination must use up-to-date information to adjust its recommendations according to dynamic changing circumstances in tourist activities or to specific user needs. When such changes occur, the system evaluates whether to generate a new recommendation from scratch or to apply a re-optimisation procedure to the itineraries of the last proposal. This itinerary optimisation problem is addressed using a hybrid metaheuristic approach, which is also suitable to re-optimize recommendations following minor contextual changes. Furthermore, an adaptive mechanism must employ reinforcement learning to decide between modifying the current proposal to satisfy new constraints or running the optimisation procedure with the new constraints. This reinforcement learning approach should incorporate historical performance data to tune parameters in response to observed changes.

ID 68

INTERPRETABLE AI FOR HUMAN-CENTERED WAREHOUSE PICKING SEGMENTATION

Soriano Gonzalez, R.^{1,2}, Medina, V.^{2,3}, Men, Y.², Carracedo,
P.^{1,2}

¹Department of Applied Statistics and Operations Research and Quality, Universitat
Politécnica de València, Ferrandiz y Carbonell, s/n, Alcoy 03802, Spain

²Research Centre on Production Management and Engineering (CIGIP), Universitat
Politécnica de València, Ferrandiz y Carbonell, s/n, Alcoy 03802, Spain

³ICSO Analytics SL, 08222 Barcelona, Spain

Abstract

Manual picking operations are one of the most resource intensive and demanding processes in warehouse logistics. Previous research has mainly focused on layout optimization and worker productivity. However, less attention has been given to how customer order structures generate structural heterogeneity in operational complexity. This study proposes an interpretable artificial intelligence (AI)-based segmentation approach to support managerial decision making in manual picking environments. Using real industrial data that integrate order level, execution level, and logistical information, we construct a customer level complexity matrix. This matrix captures exposure to manual picking, line fragmentation, temporal variability, and efficiency per handled unit. Based on these dimensions, operational complexity indices are defined and unsupervised clustering techniques are applied to identify differentiated customer profiles. The results indicate that variability and fragmentation, rather than volume alone, are key drivers of picking complexity. A limited subset of customers concentrates a disproportionate share of operational impact while exhibiting structurally distinct structural patterns. The proposed approach does not automate decisions. Instead, it structures operational heterogeneity in a transparent and interpretable manner. By combining data-driven segmentation with decision-oriented metrics, the study illustrates how Human-AI collaboration can enhance managerial understanding and prioritization in real-world logistics systems.

ID 71

BEHAVIOURAL SIMULATION OF CONSUMER SEGMENTS USING DIGITAL TWINS

Peñarroya-Farell, M.¹, Vaziri, M.¹, Casas, H.¹, Miralles, F.¹¹Ramon Llull University

Abstract

Digital twins have become an important paradigm in engineering and industrial systems, enabling the digital replication of physical assets in order to simulate performance, test interventions, and optimize outcomes before real-world deployment. More recently, the concept has begun to extend beyond physical systems toward the modeling of human behavior in digital environments. In marketing and consumer research, the emerging concept of a Digital Twin of a Customer (DToC) proposes the creation of computational agents capable of simulating the decision-making patterns of specific consumer segments.

Such models could allow organizations to test marketing messages, product propositions, or user experience designs before deploying them in real markets. However, despite growing interest in AI-driven consumer simulation, the DToC concept remains largely conceptual and lacks systematic validation frameworks. Existing research on customer digital twins has primarily focused on applications in personalization and customer experience management, with limited attention to the methodological problem of validating whether simulated agents reproduce real behavioral responses.

Consumer decision-making research suggests that behavioral patterns emerge from the interaction of psychological, cognitive, and social mechanisms. Personality traits influence how individuals process information and evaluate risk, while attitudes, intentions, and perceived behavioral control shape behavioral outcomes. Behavioral economics further demonstrates that individuals often rely on heuristics and bounded rationality when evaluating complex choices, leading to systematic patterns in judgment and decision-making. Together, these mechanisms suggest that consumer segments may be represented through structured behavioral parameters capable of generating consistent decision patterns when exposed to specific stimuli.

Building on this theoretical foundation, the present study conceptualizes the Digital Twin of a Customer as a parameterized behavioral model capable of generating simulated responses to marketing stimuli. Rather than attempting to replicate individual consumers, the objective is to approximate the response structures characteristic of defined consumer segments.

The central research question guiding this study is therefore:

RQ: Can a Digital Twin of a Customer reproduce the behavioral response patterns of real consumer segments when exposed to controlled marketing stimuli?

To address this question, the study adopts a controlled experimental design in which real participants and simulated agents representing the same segments are exposed to identical marketing stimuli. Participants evaluate a series of hypothetical product propositions presented through systematically varied marketing messages. The same stimuli are then evaluated by Digital Twins configured with the behavioral parameters associated with the corresponding segment.

The study tests two hypotheses derived from construct validation principles:

H1: Digital Twins of Customers will produce stable response patterns across repeated simulations when exposed to identical stimuli.

H2: The response structures generated by Digital Twins will align with the aggregate behavioral patterns observed among real participants belonging to the same consumer segment.

To operationalize these hypotheses, the study introduces a simulation-based validation protocol that compares human and AI-generated responses under identical experimental conditions, enabling systematic assessment of behavioral alignment between real users and their simulated counterparts.

This research contributes to the emerging intersection of artificial intelligence, marketing science, and behavioral modeling by introducing a methodological framework for validating AI-based consumer simulations. If validated, Digital Twins of Customers could become a valuable tool for testing marketing strategies, user experience designs, and decision environments before real-world deployment.

ID 72

A MIXED INTEGER PROGRAMMING APPROACH FOR COST-OPTIMAL HETEROGENEOUS NETWORK PLANNING

Escoto, M.¹, García-Sánchez, A.², Juan, A.¹, Panadero, J.³¹CIGIP, Universitat Politècnica de València, Alcoy 03801, Spain²Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid 28006, Spain³Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Bellaterra 08193, Spain

Abstract

This paper presents a mixed-integer linear programming formulation for the cost-optimal planning of 4G/5G heterogeneous networks. The model minimizes capital expenditure while meeting coverage and capacity demands across different technology layers, specifically 4G and 5G. It explicitly incorporates existing infrastructure, allowing for the upgrade of installed base stations and the deployment of new ones in candidate locations. The proposed formulation is evaluated on realistic urban-scale instances, demonstrating its ability to deliver optimal network plans for small to medium-sized areas. Results confirm the model's effectiveness in balancing infrastructure reuse and new deployment under budget constraints, providing a rigorous foundation for automated network planning.

ID 73

A GENDER LENS ON TRANSPORT APPLICATIONS IN BUSINESS ANALYTICS AND OPERATIONS RESEARCH

Carroll, P.¹, Amerehi, F.¹¹University College Dublin, Ireland

Abstract

Business Analytics (BA) and Operations Research (OR) offer scientific approaches to managing complex systems. They enable managers to make better decisions by modelling the systems, designing algorithms to solve the mathematical models and extracting insights from the solutions to recommend actions. There is an implicit assumption that the models and solution techniques to support decision makers are objective, fair and unbiased. There is a significant gap and research opportunity at the gender/BA/OR nexus to explore this assumption. We propose and demonstrate a structured Gender. Analysis workflow for a sample transportation problem and highlight the benefits of including gender dimensions in the design and implementation of BA/OR models.

ID 75

A DECISION SUPPORT MODULE FOR ENVIRONMENTAL-DRIVEN SUPPLIER SELECTION IN MANUFACTURING PROCUREMENT

Vincenzi, M.¹, Rodigari, L.¹, Leone, D.¹, Fontana, A.¹, Pirota, M.¹,
Landolfi, G.¹

*¹University of Applied Sciences and Arts of Southern Switzerland (SUPSI),
Department of Innovative Technologies, Lugano, Switzerland*

Abstract

The transition toward circular and low-carbon supply chains increasingly requires procurement processes to systematically integrate environmental considerations, material criticality, and regulatory compliance into supplier selection. However, existing decision-support solutions typically rely on static, product or enterprise-level assessments that are not integrated with the Request-for-Quotation (RFQ) workflows and rarely enable real-time, process-based customisation of sustainability criteria.

This paper introduces the Manufacturing Supplier's Intelligence Module (MSIM), a microservice-based decision-support tool that integrates parametric Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), material criticality indicators (Critical Raw Materials and Substances of Very High Concern), and regulatory compliance screening (REACH, RoHS) as a service exploitable by digital procurement platforms. The proposed methodology combines compliance filtering with a transparent multi-criteria aggregation model to generate normalised sustainability scores and real-time comparative supplier rankings. The proposed approach is implemented as a modular service-based architecture that integrates a marketplace, a sustainability platform, and a ranking engine.

The article concludes by presenting a concrete use case of the service in the procurement sector with a real purchasing platform, demonstrating the feasibility of obtaining consistent sustainability-based rankings alongside traditional price-based evaluations. The results show how the module improves transparency, comparability, and decision quality in sustainability-focused supplier selection.

ID 76

A MODE-AVAILABILITY CONSTRAINED VARIANT AND UNCERTAINTY-AWARE EVALUATION PROCEDURE FOR FLOATING CATCHMENT AREA METHODS

Valentine, R.¹, Grobler, J.¹*¹Department of Industrial Engineering, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South
Africa*

Abstract

Floating catchment area models are widely used to quantify spatial accessibility by relating population demand to provider supply under travel impedance. This paper presents a variant tailored to an urban developing-region banking context, where access is mediated through a constrained set of transport modes and self-service onboarding kiosks. As current multi-modal methods do not adequately represent the constrained nature of modal availability in this context, the mode-availability constrained three-step floating catchment area variant is proposed. Results are presented with an uncertainty-aware evaluation following a rigorous parameter selection process. The method is demonstrated using a large urban case study with re-grained population grids, a banking kiosk network, and multi-modal travel times.

ID 77

HUMAN-CENTRIC DECISION SUPPORT FOR SMART FACTORIES: A MULTIMODAL APPROACH TO HUMAN-MACHINE INTERACTION

Fumagalli, F.¹, Sana, S.¹, Pellegrini, A.¹, Forni, A.¹, Mazzolini, M.¹¹J&W Srl, Via Bachelet 1, 27019 Villanterio (PV), Italy

Abstract

Industrial manufacturing is rapidly increasing in technological sophistication: machines are more and more complex and interconnected, and automation is advancing exponentially to ensure optimized performance and ever-higher quality standards. However, in many factories, the operator's decision-making capabilities have not evolved at the same pace. This creates an ever-widening decision-making gap: operators are asked to diagnose, decide, and intervene in socio-technical systems whose complexity exceeds the cognitive tools and contextual information available on the shop floor. The risk is that human operators will be marginalized in the production system, when they should remain essential players in the chain, performing increasingly high-value tasks. Human skills, decision-making capabilities, and adaptability should continue to play a crucial role in ensuring productivity, safety, and operational resilience. J&W addresses this gap through a human-centric manufacturing philosophy, in which value is created by structured human-machine collaboration rather than by excluding operators from the cycle. This article presents a human-centric approach to smart factory design. The proposed framework integrates wearable notification systems, industrial data collection platforms, and AI-based assistants to improve human-machine interaction on the factory floor. The architecture is designed to support operators in monitoring complex production environments and making informed decisions based on contextual information. The proposed concepts are demonstrated within the Human-Centric Manufacturing Lab (HCM Lab), an industrial demonstrator that combines transport systems, collaborative robots, and autonomous mobile robots in a fashion intralogistics order-picking scenario. The article discusses the system architecture, the automation framework, and the experimental activities carried out in the laboratory.

ID 78

LARGE LANGUAGE MODEL BASED ENTITY RELATION MAPPING FOR SUPPLY CHAIN VISIBILITY

Sahin, B.¹, Inan, E.¹, Ozturk, C.²*¹Izmir Institute of Technology, Department of Computer Engineering, Urla, İzmir,
Turkey**²Munster Technological University, Process, Energy and Transport Engineering,
Cork, Ireland*

Abstract

Modern supply chains have become globally distributed, multitiered networks, making it challenging for focal firms to fully capture their overall structure. Therefore, mapping supply chains and identifying underlying dependencies is crucial for building resilient and viable supply chains, as it helps manage network fragmentation and enhances overall supply chain visibility. Handling a large amount of data and discovering hidden relationships needs automation and high computing power as well as proprietary software that might be challenging, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises. In our proposed framework, NER and RE are treated as two sequential subtasks for the supply chain domain. In the first subtask, we apply named entity recognition to an electric vehicle company corpus to detect domain-specific entities. In the second subtask, we perform relation extraction to identify semantic relationships among the extracted entities. According to experimental results, the proposed few-shot prompting method achieves an F1 score of 0.806 across various open-source large language models, demonstrating stable and high named entity recognition performance. Additionally, the proposed 20-shot prompt-based framework consistently outperforms the external prompt-based baseline across various model architectures, achieving an F1 score of 0.649 and confirming its effectiveness in improving relation extraction performance under low-supervision settings.

ID 79

GREENET: A SIMULATION-OPTIMIZATION DECISION-SUPPORT FRAMEWORK FOR WIRELESS ACCESS POINT LOCALIZATION

Granata, D.¹, Ambrosio, G.², Dragone, R.³, Cerrone, C.⁴*¹Istituto per le Applicazioni del Calcolo "Mauro Picone", National Research Council,
via dei Taurini 19, Rome 00185 Italy**²FourClicks S.r.l. Innovative Startup, Italy**³Department of Economics, Analytics and Operations Research, University of
Klagenfurt, Austria**⁴Department of Economics and Business Studies, University of Genoa, Italy*

Abstract

The placement of Wireless Access Points (APs) in indoor environments is a critical design problem affecting signal coverage, service quality, and deployment costs. This paper presents GREENET, an application-oriented decision-support framework that combines signal propagation simulation and mathematical optimization for indoor AP placement. The platform combines a grid-based discretization of the environment with a coverage-oriented Integer Linear Programming (ILP) model, which determines device locations while accounting for signal attenuation, hardware availability, and global installation limits. Computational experiments were carried out to assess both the validity of the proposed system and the performance of the ILP model under different device availability constraints, considering indoor floor layouts ranging

from simple to structurally complex configurations in order to analyze the system's limitations. The proposed framework provides an integrated simulation-optimization pipeline that bridges modeling realism and analytical decision support, enabling data-driven decision-making for indoor wireless network planning.

ID 80

A CONTEXT-ENRICHED CAPACITATED VEHICLE ROUTING FRAMEWORK: INTEGRATING OPTIMIZATION, GEOSPATIAL INTELLIGENCE, AND ADMINISTRATIVE ANALYTICS

Saiz, M.^{1,2}, Calvet, L.³

¹*Operations, Innovation & Technology Management Department, ESADE Business School, Barcelona, 08034, Spain*

²*weOptimize, Tarragona, 43700, Spain*

³*Department of Systems Engineering & Telecommunication, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 08202 Sabadell, Spain*

Abstract

This paper presents a hybrid methodology for solving the Capacitated Vehicle Routing Problem (CVRP) while augmenting optimized routes with contextual and administrative intelligence. The proposed framework integrates a Clarke–Wright savings construction algorithm operating on either Haversine-based direct distances or OSRM road-distance matrices. Beyond route optimization, a semantic enrichment layer generates per-route and per-segment contextual data, including estimated times of arrival (ETAs), weather conditions, and traffic information. To enhance territorial interpretability, an administrative enrichment module performs municipality tracing through a two-stage geospatial sampling process and extracts associated provinces and province-capital relationships. The system is implemented as a scalable web-based CVRP platform developed in Python using Azure Functions, coupled with an interactive Leaflet-based user interface. A modular API architecture is introduced, consisting of a base optimization endpoint and a dedicated municipality enrichment endpoint capable of post-processing precomputed CVRP solutions. User-facing analytics provide interactive map visualizations with segment-level and route-level administrative vectors, alongside fallback and diagnostic mechanisms. An illustrative case study demonstrates the operational feasibility and analytical value of integrating optimization with contextual geospatial intelligence, highlighting the potential of this hybrid approach for advanced logistics planning and decision support.

ID 81

TOWARDS PLANNERS SEGMENTATION IN REAL- WORLD VEHICLE ROUTING PROBLEMS

Simone, S.¹, Bettinelli, A.², Ceselli, A.¹

¹*Dipartimento di Informatica, Università degli Studi di Milano, Via Celoria 18, 20133
Milan, Italy*

²*OPTIT S.r.l., Via Mazzini, 82, 40138 Bologna (BO), Italy*

Abstract

Motivated by the search for methods to ease the editing process which human planners need to undertake, real world decision support systems in transportation are interactive: automatic tools produce optimized solutions, which are given to human planners, that may either confirm them verbatim for implementation, or perform edits to adapt them to context, needs and preferences. To ease such an editing step, we investigate which phenomena are most likely to trigger edits: implicit preferences, which do not depend on the specific planner, or implicit attitude with respect to the optimization tool, which does depend on the individual. We propose data-driven models and targeted experiments on real transportation data. Our experiments suggest digital tool attitude to be stronger than implicit preferences.

ID 82

LEAFS: LINEAR EDGE-TO-CLOUD LATENCY-AWARE FORMULATION FOR SERVICE PLACEMENT

Bertoncini, A.¹, Ceselli, A.¹, Quadri, C.¹*¹Università degli Studi di Milano, Computer Science Department, Via Celoria 18, Milan, Italy*

Abstract

Latency-critical applications such as Autonomous Vehicle Driving Services (AVDS) are increasingly implemented as microservice-based systems deployed over heterogeneous edge-to-cloud infrastructures. The resulting deployment problem can be modeled as a Virtual Network Function Placement Problem (VNFPP) with strict end-to-end latency and resource constraints. When modeling both computational placement and communication interactions among dependent microservices, the resulting optimization problem involves binary quadratic terms that significantly increase computational complexity. This paper proposes a linear reformulation of a VNF placement model for latency-aware microservice deployment under fixed routing. Starting from a binary quadratic formulation, we introduce a dependency-based MILP model in which decision variables represent the deployment of service dependencies on pairs of physical nodes. The reformulation eliminates quadratic terms while preserving the semantics of the original problem. The resulting linear model provides an effective optimization framework for analyzing latency-constrained microservice placement in edge-cloud infrastructures and highlights the structural advantages of dependency-based linear reformulations for VNF placement problems.

ID 83

RECENT AI APPROACHES FOR ONCOLOGICAL DISEASE DIAGNOSIS: AN OVERVIEW AND EMERGING FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Aiello, F.², Maccioni, R.², Tufano, R.¹¹University of Salerno, Giovanni Paolo II Street 132, 84084 Fisciano, SA, Italy²Math Biology, Diogeniano di Eraclea Street 89, 00124 Rome, RM, Italy

Abstract

Cancer diagnosis remains a central challenge in modern medicine, requiring the analysis of increasingly complex and heterogeneous biomedical data. In recent years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques have shown significant potential in supporting oncological diagnosis by identifying informative patterns in large-scale medical datasets.

Driven by these motivations, this paper provides a narrative overview of recent technological trends in AI-based oncological diagnosis, with a particular emphasis on non-classical machine learning approaches. After introducing the main categories of biomedical data commonly used in cancer diagnosis, we review several emerging computational paradigms, including deep learning architectures, foundation models, and multimodal learning frameworks capable of integrating heterogeneous data sources.

Finally, we outline promising future research directions, highlighting the growing importance of multimodal data integration and the exploration of novel physiological and metabolic signals that may complement traditional diagnostic information. The aim of this work is to provide a technologically oriented perspective on current developments and future opportunities in AI-assisted oncological diagnosis.

ID 84

TAG EXTRACTION FROM MEDICAL HISTORY THROUGH LLMs

Maccioni, R.², Tufano, R.¹, Magliaro, A.¹¹University of Salerno, Giovanni Paolo II Street 132, 84084 Fisciano, SA, Italy²Math Biology, Diogeniano di Eraclea Street 89, 00124 Rome, RM, Italy

Abstract

The growing amount of clinical information poses significant challenges for healthcare professionals, who must interpret large volumes of unstructured data during clinical practice. In particular, patient medical histories contain valuable diagnostic information but usually the extraction of relevant clinical information is time-consuming and cognitively demanding. Recent advances in generative artificial intelligence, particularly Large Language Models (LLMs), offer new opportunities to automatically analyze and structure such information.

This study investigates the potential of LLMs to extract informative clinical tags from free-text medical histories integrating generative AI into clinical data processing workflows. Several LLMs are evaluated under two different prompting strategies. The experimental results show that LLMs can effectively identify clinically relevant information from patient medical histories, achieving strong performance.

These findings suggest that LLMs can serve as supportive tools in clinical environments, helping to reduce the cognitive burden on physicians while transforming unstructured medical histories into structured data. Such structured information may be implemented in AI models and Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) to enable more efficient analysis and data-driven clinical support.

ID 86

MACHINE LEARNING-DRIVEN BI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION OF HETEROLOGOUS AND HOMOLOGOUS COVID-19 VACCINE DISTRIBUTION NETWORK

Ghassemi Tari, T.¹, Jahed, A.², Moussavi, M.¹*¹Departments of Botany and Zoology, University of British Columbia, Vancouver,
British Columbia, Canada**²Department of Industrial Engineering, Business Administration and Statistics, ETSII,
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Madrid, Spain*

Abstract

Abstract. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) triggered the COVID-19 pandemic and created an urgent global need for effective vaccines. Homologous vaccination (repeated doses of the same vaccine) and heterologous vaccination (mix-and-match regimens) emerged as two key strategies. Clinical studies evaluated multiple vaccine combinations for primary and booster doses and measured cellular and humoral immune responses using Immunoglobulin-G (IgG) antibody levels. Findings remain mixed: some regimens induce stronger immune responses with heterologous boosters, while others show comparable or higher responses with homologous strategies. Experimental data are limited for many combinations, especially newer vaccines, and few studies integrate vaccine effectiveness into planning. Machine learning (ML) supports data-driven healthcare management. A K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) regression model predicts IgG responses for all homologous and heterologous combinations among six COVID-19 vaccines using a peer-reviewed dataset. Predicted values inform a COVID-19 vaccine supply chain network that aims to minimize vaccine supply and distribution costs while maximizing social benefits by enhancing vaccination effectiveness. This model optimizes COVID-19 vaccine supply for homologous and heterologous strategies, tackling logistical bottlenecks, shortages, demand gaps, and vaccination effectiveness. By linking predictive modeling with supply chain optimization, this study provides a framework to evaluate vaccine strategies comprehensively and support efficient, effective COVID-19 vaccination planning.

ID 90

AN ONTOLOGY FOR MANUFACTURING OPERATIONS AS A SERVICE

Mula, J.¹, Guerrero, B.², Guerrero-Martínez, M.¹, Almendros, J.²*¹Universitat Politècnica de València, Research Centre on Production Management and Engineering, Plaza Ferrándiz y Carbonell, s/n, 03801, Alcoy, Alicante, Spain**²Universitat Politècnica de València, Research Centre on Production Management and Engineering, Camino de Vera, s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain*

Abstract

A manufacturing-as-a-service (MaaS) aims to enable decentralised and data-driven manufacturing operations through a digital platform. A MaaS implementation requires to be flexible, interoperable and scalable in order to manage a number of problems, problem subtypes and their variants and even with a wide variety of problem sizes. The EU project UniMaaS (Unified Modelling and Automated Scheduling for Manufacturing as a Service) aims to deliver a platform for flexible, agile and decentralised manufacturing, embracing the MaaS paradigm in four industrial pilots: aircraft maintenance, automotive seat manufacturing, 3D construction printing and distribution logistics and warehousing. As a preliminary step to the implementation of MaaS, we propose identifying and classifying the subtypes of problems, as well as developing the relevant ontologies for the problems identified in the UniMaaS industrial pilots. These problem classifications and ontology definitions are essential for data exchange, model integration and decision-making workflows across diverse manufacturing systems and stakeholders.

ID 91

REDUCING BIOLOGICAL UNCERTAINTY IN PREVENTIVE ONCOLOGY: A BAYESIAN DECISION FRAMEWORK INTEGRATING DYNAMIC METABOLIC PROFILING (DMA-PPOP)

Aiello, F.¹, Pavese, I.¹¹*Math Biology srl, 00125 Rome, Italy*

Abstract

Preventive oncology relies largely on epidemiological risk models and population-based screening strategies to estimate individual cancer probability. While these approaches have significantly improved early detection and risk stratification, they remain primarily based on static variables that only partially capture the current biological condition of an individual. This limitation becomes particularly relevant in intermediate-risk scenarios, where preventive decisions must be made under conditions of residual biological uncertainty. This paper int+F63+F58

ID 92

AI-BASED OPTIMIZATION FOR FACILITY LOCATION UNDER CHANGING CAPACITY CONDITIONS

Men, Y.¹, Perez-Bernabeu, E.¹, Juan, A.¹

¹CIGIP – ValgrAI, Universitat Politècnica de València, Ferrandiz-Carbonell, 03801
Alcoy, Spain

Abstract

Organizations often need to decide where to locate facilities such as service centers, emergency units, or infrastructure nodes. These decisions aim to spread facilities across a region while ensuring that total capacity meets demand requirements. Standard optimization models support these decisions but usually assume that each facility has a fixed and known capacity. In practice, this assumption is often not realistic. Capacity can vary depending on local conditions, interactions with nearby facilities, and operational factors. As a result, solutions that look optimal on paper may fail to deliver enough capacity in real settings. This work proposes a new approach that combines machine learning and optimization to address this issue. A predictive model is used to estimate the effective capacity of each facility based on its context. These estimates are then embedded within an exact optimization method that selects facility locations. During the decision process, the model updates capacity estimates and helps avoid choices that would lead to insufficient overall capacity. The approach is suitable for organizations that need to make strategic location decisions in environments where capacity is uncertain or context-dependent.

ID 93

BEYOND STATISTICAL CONVERGENCE: OPTIMIZED SEMANTIC MODELS FOR STRATEGIC MARKETING

Solaini, R.¹*¹Department of Visual Arts, Istituto Europeo del Design, Milan, Italy*

Abstract

Data-driven marketing can result in overtrusting the effectiveness of AI-driven decisions. Increasing data granularity and growing computational power do not automatically produce more appropriate decisions, while the proliferation of weakly informative variables may reduce the intelligibility of the overall scenario.

Walter Quattrociocchi has recently outlined the epistemological limits of AI, describing it as a regime of knowledge based on statistical convergence of linguistic tokens, not founded on causal relationships with predictive value. A long-lasting issue, originally defined by David Hume and developed by Nelson Goodman, who maintained that the reliability of a generalization depends on its conceptualization.

The same point has been highlighted by Luciano Floridi, stressing the need to organize data into local patterns, so as to make them fully informative and cognitively productive, thus also shaping the optimal interface between Artificial and Human intelligence.

Frame Semantics, originally developed by Charles Fillmore and later formalized in the FrameNet research program, becomes methodologically relevant. By explaining lexical variation as a function of the semantic frames in which lexical items occur, it makes it possible to formalize recurrent micro-arguments in a format readable both by computers and by humans.

The present contribution advances an operational proposal for strategic marketing: by combining quantitative KPIs with semantically modeled symbolic variables, it allows to move beyond optimization and build decision frameworks able to integrate marketing efficiency with branding strategy, to support not only the optimization of decisions, but the governance of decision-making itself.

ID 96

ABSOLUT VODKA: FROM HUMAN INTELLIGENCE TO HUMAN-AI COLLABORATION IN REAL-WORLD MARKETING DECISION- MAKING

Moll, I.¹, Montaña, J.¹*¹ESADE Business School, Avenida de Pedralbes 60-62, 08034, Barcelona, Spain*

Abstract

This paper examines how Human–AI collaboration supports real-world decision-making in marketing-driven innovation through a longitudinal case study of Absolut Vodka. The study focuses on how Generative AI (GenAI) tools are currently being used to strengthen and extend a marketing-driven innovation strategy originally defined during the brand’s U.S. market entry in the late 1970s and 1980s. Drawing on archival material, insider insights from the original advertising development, and contemporary industry documentation, the analysis shows that Absolut’s AI initiatives are concentrated on the front stage of branding and consumer experience, particularly in promotion, experiential marketing, brand visibility in AI-mediated discovery environments, and symbolic product meaning. Rather than replacing human judgment, GenAI functions as a decision-support and creativity-augmentation layer embedded within key marketing decision domains. The paper contributes to the literature on Human–AI collaboration by illustrating how AI can reinforce strategic continuity in marketing-driven innovation, while also identifying areas of unrealised potential for deeper AI integration into back-end decision systems.

ID 97

INCORPORATING AI IN ECOSYSTEMS GOVERNANCE: ARCHETYPES AND IMPLEMENTATION FRAMEWORK

Rodriguez, P.¹, Lopez-Lopez, D.², Juan, A.³*¹Dept. of Computer Science, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, 08018 Barcelona, Spain**²Dept. of Marketing, ESADE Business School, 08172 Sant Cugat**³CIGIP, Universitat Politècnica de València, 03801 Alcoy, Spain*

Abstract

The rise of corporate ecosystems is transforming value creation; existing governance frameworks remain anchored in bilateral relationships and human-mediated coordination. As artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities advance beyond decision support, a critical question emerges: how should CEOs structure corporate ecosystems' governance when AI can process multidimensional interdependencies that exceed human cognitive capacity? This article addresses this gap by proposing a governance-oriented framework that positions AI as an orchestrator: an active agent shaping partner selection, role configuration, and coordination mechanisms. We make three contributions. First, integrate portfolio decision theory, ecosystem governance, and algorithmic agency to conceptualize AI as a governance mechanism in interdependent systems. Second, we introduce three governance archetypes: centralized orchestration, distributed, and hybrid governance and specify the conditions under which each is most effective. Third, we develop a multi-layer implementation framework addressing strategic, tactical, and operational levels. Together, these contributions address five key research gaps: (1) how AI mediates governance relationships, (2) how to allocate responsibility when AI exercises governed autonomy, (3) how to evaluate partner configurations, (4) how to build collective trust in multi-stakeholder systems, and (5) how to translate conceptual frameworks into practice. The paper provides a foundation for understanding AI as a structural component of ecosystem governance and offers actionable guidance for executives navigating complex, interdependent environments.

